

A Medium Model Leading to Analogy of Major Physics Laws

Ting Yi
(tingyi.physics@gmail.com)
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Ting Yi
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Abstract: The attempt of this paper is to suggest a new theoretical medium to support the efforts of building particle models as mechanical field structures. The medium model is based on two simple fundamental assumptions. All the properties of the medium, as counterparts in this medium of the well-known physics laws, including energy and momentum conservation, Lorentz transformation and special relativity, electromagnetic interaction, etc., are derived from these two assumptions. Possible steady solutions of the field equations, as well as the feasibility of interpreting these solutions as particles, are also briefly discussed.

Keywords: ether field; medium model; Lorentz transformation; relativity; electromagnetic field

The effort to find the fundamental of particles and interactions has a long history and has never ended. In parallel to the quantum mechanics - standard model - string theory approach, there are some “non-mainstream” attempts to model elementary particles as certain kind of field structures. About 150 years ago, William Thomson (Lord Kelvin) made the “vortex atom” conjecture^{[1], [2]}, and spent decades trying to approve it. Albert Einstein devoted most of his later years trying to find a uniform theory to explain particles and interactions. Many other attempts were made in more recent time. A big number of them are related to topological solitons and with knot and link structures (e.g., the Kamchatnov-Hopf soliton^[3], the Skyrme-Faddeev model^{[4], [5]}, the glueball model^[6]). V. P. Dmitriyev also made series of conjectures to interpret particles as structures in a mechanical medium^{[7], [8]}.

The purpose of this paper is to develop a simple but rich medium model, which potentially can serve as a new medium for the structures to interpret particles and interactions. We shall borrow a convenient name and call this medium ether field. However, we shall not employ any pre-set property of the historical concept of ether as medium of light, nor shall we pre-assume any known physical laws and apply them in a pre-set manner. The field model is based on two basic assumptions. From them we will derive a series of properties of the medium, which interestingly are almost exact analog of the basic physical laws, including momentum and energy conservation (thus the motion laws and equations), Lorentz transformation (thus special relativity), electromagnetic field, and a “gravity-like” interaction. If soliton-like solutions of the field equations exist (which in general is yet to be proved but some examples are given in this paper) and can be interpreted as particles, these properties of the medium potentially will provide explanations for the corresponding physical laws.

§1 Ether, as a New Medium Model

Consider a scalar, non-negative real function of space and time, denoted by $\Omega(\vec{r}, t)$. Borrowing a convenient name, we call Ω ether field, and call the “amount” of ether field over a region of space, $Q = \int_V \Omega dv$ ($V \subset R^3$), ether. In other words, Ω is considered as density of ether over space.

We will assume that ether conserves. This is the first of the two fundamental assumptions for ether field. Intuitively, this means a block of ether can move from one place to another, and can contract or expand, but the total amount (as integral of field strength over the volume) remains the same.

Strictly speaking, description of conservation relies on a reference system to enable the measurement of space (size, volume), time and speed. So this assumption actually implies the existence of such a reference system, and implies that speed (velocity) can be defined over each point of the field.

Under this assumption (hereafter in this paper we will call it “ether conservation assumption” or ECA), the following continuity equation holds:

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t} \Omega + \nabla \cdot (\Omega \vec{u}) = 0. \quad (1.1)$$

For a block of stationary field, we further define energy as $E = \int_V \Omega^2(\vec{r}) dv$. Obviously, here we take square of ether field strength as “energy density”. Note that this is just a formalistic definition, and “energy” is another borrowed name. It does not bring any pre-assumed property, e.g., conservation. Indeed, conservation of energy will be derived from the basic assumptions.

Also note that this definition is only for stationary field. Energy of dynamic field will be defined in a later section.

Now let us consider a rectangular block of stationary and uniform field Ω_0 , with L as length and s as area of the left side S (Fig. 1-1). If S moves towards right a small distance δ and other sides remain in the same positions, also, assuming this procedure is quasi-static, i.e., field remains stationary and uniform all the time, according to ECA, after the movement of S , field strength becomes

$$\Omega' = \Omega_0 \frac{L}{L - \delta},$$

and energy of the block becomes

$$E' = \Omega'^2 s(L - \delta).$$

As $\delta \ll L$, the change of energy is

$$\Delta E = E' - E_0 = \Omega_0^2 sL \frac{\delta}{L - \delta} \approx \Omega_0^2 s \delta.$$

Fig. 1-1: Quasi-static movement of the left side of an ether block

There is no exchange of ether between both sides of S. But the quasi-static movement of S compresses (if $\delta > 0$) or expands (if $\delta < 0$) the field in the block, thus causes energy to increase or decrease in it. The amount of increased/decreased energy equals to product of square of field strength, area of S and distance of movement in normal direction, but is independent to volume of the field block (as long as $L \gg \delta$ and the procedure is quasi-static) .

The same calculation applies to a general case of an area element (i.e., an area of interface) moving quasi-statically in a stationary field Ω . Assuming that ether does not pass through the area element, energy will increase on one side and decrease on the other side, by the same amount. This is equivalent to an energy exchanging between the two sides of that area element, and the amount of exchanged energy is

$$\Delta E \approx \Omega^2 s \delta = P_0 s \delta. \text{ (here } P_0 \triangleq \Omega^2 \text{).}$$

Obviously, if we make analogy between ether field to ideal gases, we can define P_0 as pressure of stationary field. Then the energy change of each side during the quasi-static procedure equals to product of area and pressure (i.e., press) multiplying the distance of movement, i.e., equals to the “work” done against the press. In other words, if we define pressure, press and work in the above way, energy change will be equal to work done against press. In this sense, “mechanical energy” of stationary ether field conserves in the quasi-static procedures.

Note that for ether field, “energy” by definition means solely the “mechanical energy”, whose volume density equals to square of field strength. Unlike gases, there is no temperature, inner energy or other form of energy considered for ether field. Thus the conservation of “mechanical energy” described above means conservation of energy for stationary field.

As a side note, the above definitions of pressure, press and work are following the definition of energy. In principle, we can also define energy in a more general way as $\tilde{E} = \int_v \Omega^n dv$ (n can be any real number greater than 1), and the definition of pressure would change accordingly to $\tilde{P} = (n-1)\Omega^n$. Then by applying ECA, energy conservation of stationary field can be derived in a similar way.

In the rest of this paper, unless specially mentioned, we will only consider the case of $n=2$.

§2 Sound Propagation Assumption

According to ECA and the definition of energy, when a block of ether contracts or expands, ether remains the same, but energy varies when volume changes. For same amount of ether, the smaller the volume, the greater the energy.

When field is not uniform, the regions where field is stronger have higher “energy density” (and “pressure”). A natural supposition is that ether will diffuse from high pressure regions to low pressure regions.

The diffusion will cause perturbations in the field, similar to density perturbations (sounds) propagating in gases. In the latter case, speed of sound is a property of the gas. It varies for different gases and in different temperatures. In ether field however, there is no temperature or other factors to impact the speed. Therefore, we will assume that sounds (perturbations) propagate in a constant speed, denoted as c , in ether field. This is the second basic assumption. We will call it “sound propagation assumption”, or SPA, hereafter in this paper.

It’s necessary to clarify the meaning of “constant speed” here.

As shown in Fig. 2-1, assuming the field is stationary and uniform before perturbed, and a plane-wave perturbation, as a step ε on field strength, is propagating from left to right, the assumption in this case is that the step (or the “wave front”) moves in a fixed speed c , regardless of strength of Ω and ε .

Fig. 2-1: A perturbation propagating in a flat ether field

Take a sample area, s , from the wave front plane S . As the field on the right side of S is stationary, the ether flow to support this area to move in speed c is $J = \varepsilon s c$. To meet ECA, the field on the left side of S , which is $\Omega + \varepsilon$ in strength, needs to be moving in certain speed, v , to provide this flow. This requires $v = \frac{\varepsilon c}{\Omega + \varepsilon}$. SPA here means that c is a fixed value, and ε , Ω and v satisfy this equation.

Furthermore, if the field Ω is moving in an initial speed v_0 before perturbed (assume $v_0 < c$), in other words, the perturbation is propagating in a moving field, the SPA assumption here is that the wave front still travels in the speed of c (relative to the observer, rather than to the field).

In this case, the fields on both sides of the wave front are moving, and the “net ether flow” to support the movement of wave front is provided by the difference of flows between the two sides. If field speed on the left side of the wave front is v , ECA requires

$$(\Omega + \varepsilon)vs - \Omega v_0 s = \varepsilon s c, \text{ or } \frac{v}{c}(\Omega + \varepsilon) - \frac{v_0}{c}\Omega = \varepsilon,$$

and SPA in this case is that c is the same constant value as in the stationary field.

Obviously, this is different than the case of sound in gases. In gas case, the fixed sound speed is relative to the gas. If the gas is moving, the speed of sound in the gas relative to the observer is the (Galilean or Lorentz) transformation of speed of the gas and the sound speed in stationary gas. In the

suggested ether field here however, SPA assumes that sound (perturbation caused by field ununiformity) travels in a constant speed relative to the observer, even in a field that is moving before sound comes.

In certain degree, this is rather the “ether version” of the light speed constancy principle in relativity. Note that in the ether field model here, light and photon are supposed to be “high level” phenomenon, and are not directly related to perturbations/sounds in the field (a rough conjecture about light and photon will be discussed in the latest section). So c here is just the speed of sound in ether field, and is (temporarily) not directly related to light. But if we put c in the similar position as speed of light, sound propagation assumption here is obviously similar to light speed constancy principle in special relativity.

In ideal gases, sound speed can be derived from mechanical properties (i.e., elasticity and inertia). Here in ether field, we set constancy of sound speed an assumption. Thus, this assumption implies certain mechanical properties of the field. This essential assumption (i.e., SPA), together with the ether conservation assumption (ECA), will lead to energy and momentum conservation and other mechanical properties of ether field, which are to be discussed in the following sections.

§3 Acceleration of Ether

With ECA and SPA, let us consider in a dynamic way (instead of the quasi-static way in §1) the change of a stationary and uniform rectangular field block. Assume that the left side, S , moves towards right in a steady speed θ (assuming $\theta < c$) within a short period of time τ (Fig. 3-1). S is considered as the interface between ether inside and outside of the block, thus, no ether will pass through it. The movement of S will push the ether next to it towards right. This ether, adding to the field in the block, will cause ununiformity and form a perturbation, which will then propagate to the right, in sound speed.

Fig. 3-1: Perturbation caused by side of a field block moving in a fixed speed

If there was no sound propagation, the ether pushed to the right would have accumulated unlimitedly. Sound propagation spreads out the ether, limits the accumulation, and sets the field strength to a level in which the ether flow of sound propagation and the flow pushed to the right by movement of S counterbalance.

To make the discussion simple, for one-dimensional case, we will assume that movements are parallel to x direction, and respectively use positive and negative speed values to describe movements on $+x$ and $-x$ directions.

The amplitude of perturbation, ε , can be calculated from ECA. As S moves in speed of θ , the total amount of ether pushed towards right per unit time is $\Omega\theta s$. This equals to the amount of ether spread out with the perturbation per unit time. That is

$$\Omega\theta s = \varepsilon(c - \theta)s.$$

$$\text{Thus we have } \varepsilon = \frac{\theta}{c - \theta}\Omega \text{ or } \Omega + \varepsilon = \frac{c}{c - \theta}\Omega. \quad (3.1)$$

ε can also be calculated from equivalence of ether on initial and end states of the block. At $t=0$, the block lays between point A and Point C (Fig. 3-1); field strength is Ω and the block is stationary. At $t=\tau$, the block is now between point B and Point C, with field strength of $\Omega+\varepsilon$. Equivalence of ether on these two states gives the same result as (3.1).

Strictly speaking, ε here is the average amplitude of the perturbation. But according to (3.1), ε is decided by θ (and Ω). While θ keeps steady, ε is stable. If we set τ a very short time period, ε would be the instantaneous amplitude.

At $t=\tau$, ether in the block should be moving in certain speed, v , to provide flow to support the sound propagation. That means

$$(\Omega + \varepsilon)sv = \varepsilon sc$$

$$\text{or } v = \frac{\varepsilon sc}{(\Omega + \varepsilon)s} = \theta. \quad (3.2)$$

In other words, at $t=\tau$, ether in the block has already been accelerated to the same speed as side S.

Same analysis applies to the case that side S moves outwards of the block. In that case, θ is a negative value, and (3.1), (3.2) still stand. ε in this case is also negative (i.e., a negative perturbation).

Similar analysis also applies to a block with an initial speed.

Assume that the block is moving in an initial speed v_0 in x direction. At $t=0$, side S starts moving in speed θ , and keeps this steady speed until $t=\tau$ (Fig. 3-2). In this case, the extra flow caused by movement of S is $\Omega(\theta - v_0)s$. It can be a positive or a negative perturbation depending on sign of $\theta - v_0$. At $t=\tau$, the perturbation reaches point C. At the same time, what also reaches point C is the ether that was at point C_0 at $t=0$ (distance from C_0 to C is τv_0). If we take the block between A and C_0 at $t=0$ as the initial block, it becomes the block between B and C at $t=\tau$. Applying ECA we have

$$(\Omega + \varepsilon)(\tau - \tau\theta)s = \Omega(\tau - \tau v_0)s$$

or
$$\varepsilon = \frac{\theta - v_0}{c - \theta} \Omega \quad (3.3)$$

or
$$\Omega + \varepsilon = \frac{c - v_0}{c - \theta} \Omega \quad (3.4)$$

and the speed of ether in the block at $t=\tau$ is also the same as side S. i.e.,

$$v = \frac{\varepsilon s c + \Omega s v_0}{(\Omega + \varepsilon) s} = \theta. \quad (3.5)$$

Fig. 3-2: Perturbation in a non-stationary field block caused by movement of a side

We can apply (3.3) on either the upstream side or the downstream side. If ether in the block is moving away from the considered side, v_0 is positive; otherwise v_0 is negative. We can also apply (3.3) for the cases S moving inwards ($\theta > 0$) and outwards ($\theta < 0$) of the block. In a special case, if field outside the block on a side is dedicatedly “arranged” to have proper strength and speed, it is possible that the side is pushed or pulled to stop at $t=0$ and remains stationary until $t=\tau$. In this case, we have $\theta = 0$ and (3.3), (3.4), (3.5) still hold.

In summary, for a block of ether with initial speed of v_0 , ($-c < v_0 < c$), if a side perpendicular to v_0 moves in a steady speed in a period of time, the ether within the inference zone of that side (zone within distance sound travels in the time period) will be accelerated/decelerated to the same speed of the side. These accelerations/decelerations are consequences of sound propagations, ruled by ECA and SPA.

§ 4 Energy and Momentum of Dynamic Fields

With the analysis of ether acceleration/deceleration, let us further consider a block of ether with uniform strength Ω and speed v in its length direction. Same as before, denote length of the block as L and area of the left or right side as s .

Assuming at $t=0$, both sides on the left and right are pushed/pulled to stop, according to (3.3), there will be a negative and a positive perturbation on the upstream and downstream side, respectively. The

strengths of the perturbations are $\varepsilon = \pm \frac{v}{c} \Omega$. At $t=0$, these two perturbations start propagating towards each other, at speed of sound (Fig. 4-1b). At $t = \frac{L}{2c}$, they meet at the mid-point of the block (Fig. 4-1c). At this point of time, all ether in the block is stationary. The definition of stationary field energy in §1 thus applies, and we can calculate the total energy of the block as

$$E = (\Omega - \varepsilon)^2 \frac{L}{2} s + (\Omega + \varepsilon)^2 \frac{L}{2} s = (1 + \frac{v^2}{c^2}) \Omega^2 L s .$$

Fig. 4-1: A block with initial speed is “blocked” to stop on both sides

As assumed, both sides do not move after $t=0$. Thus, there is no “work” done by the sides on the block. If we define energy of a dynamic field block with speed v , field strength Ω and volume V as

$$E = (1 + \frac{v^2}{c^2}) \Omega^2 V , \quad (4.1)$$

energy of the block keeps the same at start state ($t=0$, shown in Fig. 4-1a) and end state ($t= L/(2c)$, shown in Fig. 4-1c.)

Furthermore, at any time between $t=0$ and $t= L/(2c)$, if we apply (4.1) to the moving portion of the block (between C_1 and C_2 in Fig. 4-1b) and add it to the energy of stationary portions (between A and C_1 and between C_2 and B), it can be found that the total energy stays the same at any time.

In other words, if we define energy of dynamic field as (4.1), energy conserves during this procedure.

There is also another conserved quantity in this procedure. Consider the interfaces on both left and right side. As they are both stationary after $t=0$, the definition of pressure for stationary field in § 1 applies. On the left side the pressure is $(\Omega - \varepsilon)^2$ while on the right side it is $(\Omega + \varepsilon)^2$. The time both perturbations reach the mid-point of the block is $\tau = \frac{L}{2c}$. At this time, the whole block is stationary. If we

calculate the product of pressure and time (i.e., the “impulse”), we will find the difference of it between the left and right side as

$$\Delta I = (\Omega + \varepsilon)^2 s \frac{L}{2c} - (\Omega - \varepsilon)^2 s \frac{L}{2c} = \frac{2\Omega^2}{c^2} v L s .$$

If we define $\frac{2\Omega^2}{c^2}$ as “mass density”, and define $\frac{2\Omega^2}{c^2} v$ as “momentum density”, momentum of the block at $t=0$ would be $\frac{2\Omega^2}{c^2} v L s$ and momentum at $t=\tau$ is 0 (as the whole block is stationary at $t=\tau$).

Change on momentum in this case equals to difference of impulses provided by the left and right sides during the procedure, i.e., momentum conserves.

The same conclusion could be obtained at any time between $t=0$ and $t=\tau$, by comparing momentum change in the block to net impulse provided by both sides.

§ 5 Local Energy and Momentum Conservation

With the definitions of energy and momentum for dynamic field, we can now revisit the case of a field block accelerated by movement of its side.

For the first example discussed on §3 (Fig. 3-1), on the right side, as field is stationary before the perturbation arrives, pressure is always Ω^2 . On the left side, field is not stationary. Denote the pressure there by P , and recall the start state in which field strength is Ω , speed is 0, and volume is τs , and end state in which field is $\Omega+\varepsilon$, speed is θ and volume is $(\tau - \tau\theta)s$. At $t=\tau$, on the left, pressure P has done a work of $P\tau\theta s$. The right side did not move, so there is no work done there. By letting energy change equal to sum of work done on the block, we have

$$\left(1 + \frac{\theta^2}{c^2}\right) (\Omega + \varepsilon)^2 (\tau - \tau\theta)s - \Omega^2 \tau s = P \tau \theta s .$$

Applying (3.1), we then have

$$P = \left(1 - \frac{\theta^2}{c^2}\right) (\Omega + \varepsilon)^2 . \tag{5.1}$$

In other words, if pressure at a point where field strength is Ω and speed is v is defined as

$$P = \left(1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2}\right) \Omega^2 , \tag{5.2}$$

pressure on the left side of the block satisfies (5.1) and energy conserves during the acceleration.

On the other hand, at end state, mass density is $\frac{2(\Omega + \varepsilon)^2}{c^2}$ and momentum density is $\frac{2(\Omega + \varepsilon)^2}{c^2} \theta$.

With (5.1), we can straightforwardly confirmed that change on momentum equals to net impulse provided by both sides during the acceleration, i.e., momentum conserves.

It is also straightforward to extend these conclusions to the acceleration/deceleration of a block with non-zero initial speed (shown in Fig. 3-2).

From (4.1), the total energy of a block consists of two portions: the static portion $\Omega^2 V$ and the kinetic portion $\Omega^2 \frac{v^2}{c^2} V$. These are the only two forms of energy in the field. The static energy can also be considered as a potential energy. In an imagined scenario if the ether in the block evenly permeates throughout the whole space (and there is no other ether in the space), the static energy would be equal to the work done to push the ether back to the block (quasi-statically). On the other hand, per (5.1), pressure equals to the difference between static energy density and kinetic energy density.

In summary, for uniform field blocks, in one-dimensional motions (in which acceleration or deceleration are in the same direction as initial speed), if energy, mass, momentum and pressure, work, impulse are defined in the above way, two conservation laws hold: change of energy equals to total net work done on the block; change of momentum equals to net impulse given by the sides.

The restriction of uniformity here is not substantively necessary. If field is not uniform, we can split the block into small blocks, approximatively consider each block uniform, and set time period to very short one. The above analysis still applies.

Also note that the conservations are only inside field blocks thus far. Strictly speaking, they are just local level of energy and momentum conservations. To extend them to the whole field, i.e., to global level, it's necessary to confirm that the energy/momentum a block gains/loses are exactly the same in amount the adjacent blocks lose/gain. This will be discussed on next section.

Obviously, these conservation properties depend on definitions of energy, momentum and other quantities. The conservations in this sense can be considered as mathematical inferences of those definitions. At the same time, they are also consequences of ECA and SPA. In certain degree, they can also be considered as natural properties of the theoretical medium in which ECA and SPA stand. Definitions of energy, momentum, etc. are just the proper tools to expose these properties.

Speed of sound, as speed of distribution of ununiformities, plays an important role in the procedures. Sound speed decides the amplitude of perturbations and easiness of acceleration. This explains why sound speed, mostly combined with ether speed (as the ratio of ether speed to sound speed, or the "Mach number", v/c), appears in the definitions of mass, momentum and energy.

§6 Interface and Interaction

Unlike in the gas cases, in ether field, we shall not consider anything other than ether. In other words, we consider ether as the only being in space. There is no other “object” to impact motion of ether. Changes on motion status of ether are solely caused by ether to ether interactions.

Furthermore, as a result of ether being the only being, interaction between ether is local. It only happens between parts of ether that are “touching” each other. There is no remote interaction nor other kinds of “force”, as there is no other being to act as medium for remote interaction or other kinds of force.

For an interface in the field, ether on both sides are “pushing” each other. Pressure (defined as 5.2) describes the strength of the “pushes”. According to SPA, if the “pushes” on both sides are not balancing, i.e., pressure around the interface is not uniform, the ether nearby will react to “correct” the ununiformity. The reaction/correction appears as a perturbation, or sound, and the quickness of nearby ether to be involved in the reaction/correction is prescribed by SPA with the fixed speed of sound.

So, generally speaking, it is local ununiformity that causes motion status to change. To “correct” the ununiformity, the involved ether near an unbalanced point in the field will change motion status and re-distribute. This redistribution can then impact other ether, cause new ununiformities and further changes. As series of changes going on, the effect spreads as a perturbation, at sound speed. This is the way ether interacts, and the way motion status changes.

As assumed, all these changes follow ECA and SPA. They can be considered as results of the two assumptions. Generally speaking, ECA rules how motions impact ether distributions (accumulations and decumulations), and SPA rules how ether distributions (ununiformities) impact motions. These two assumptions together form the fundamental of the “ether field theory” this paper is attempting to establish.

An “interface” or a “surface” here means an imaginal area element in the field. For convenience purpose, in further discussions, we will call a surface a Lagrangian surface or Lagrangian interface, if no ether pass through it, and call a surface/interface otherwise an Eulerian surface or Eulerian interface.

Alternatively speaking, Lagrangian interfaces in this sense are “material surfaces”, and are decided by state and motion of the field. Eulerian interfaces, on the other hand, are just geometry frames used to exam the field.

For a Lagrangian interface to be steady (stationary or moving in an unchanged speed), ECA requires normal speed of ether on both sides to be continued, and SPA requires pressures to be balanced. If at least one of these is “unbalanced”, ether around the interface will be pushed/pulled and change motion status.

Consider two respectively uniform blocks. At $t=0$, the field strength and velocity are Ω_1, v_1 and Ω_2, v_2 respectively. v_1 and v_2 are in parallel, and both blocks share a side, S , perpendicular to v_1/v_2 (Fig. 6-1). Let us check the motion status of this shared side, as a Lagrangian interface.

Fig. 6-1: Movement of an interface in the field

In a general case, v_1 and v_2 can be different and pressures on both sides of S may not be the same. In this case, S would move towards the low-pressure side, to balance the differences. Assume the speed S moves is θ , stable at least within a short period of time.

According to (3.4) and (3.5), field on both sides will be pulled/pushed to the same speed as the interface, θ , and field strength on both sides will respectively become

$$\Omega'_1 = \frac{c + v_1}{c + \theta} \Omega_1 \text{ and } \Omega'_2 = \frac{c - v_2}{c - \theta} \Omega_2. \quad (6.1)$$

Pressure is a function of field strength and speed. In this one-dimensional case, as motions are only on normal direction of the interface, equal pressure with equal normal speed means equal field strength, i.e, $\Omega'_1 = \Omega'_2$ (unless $v_1 = v_2 = c$ thus pressures are both zero).

Denote the common field strength as $\Omega' = \Omega'_1 = \Omega'_2$, with (6.1), we can obtain

$$\Omega' = \frac{1}{2} \left[\left(1 + \frac{v_1}{c}\right) \Omega_1 + \left(1 - \frac{v_2}{c}\right) \Omega_2 \right] \quad (6.2)$$

$$\theta = \frac{\left(1 + \frac{v_1}{c}\right) \Omega_1 - \left(1 - \frac{v_2}{c}\right) \Omega_2}{\left(1 + \frac{v_1}{c}\right) \Omega_1 + \left(1 - \frac{v_2}{c}\right) \Omega_2} c \quad (6.3)$$

$$\varepsilon_1 = \Omega' - \Omega_1 = \frac{1}{2} \left(-\Omega_1 \left(1 - \frac{v_1}{c}\right) + \Omega_2 \left(1 - \frac{v_2}{c}\right) \right) \quad (6.4)$$

$$\varepsilon_2 = \Omega' - \Omega_2 = \frac{1}{2} \left(\Omega_1 \left(1 + \frac{v_1}{c}\right) - \Omega_2 \left(1 + \frac{v_2}{c}\right) \right) \quad (6.5)$$

$$P' = \left(1 - \frac{\theta^2}{c^2}\right) \Omega'^2 = \left(\Omega_1 \left(1 + \frac{v_1}{c}\right) \right) \cdot \left(\Omega_2 \left(1 - \frac{v_2}{c}\right) \right) \quad (6.6)$$

P' is the balanced pressure of the field around S after it moves, and ε_1 and ε_2 are amplitudes of the two perturbations started from S towards both directions.

As pressure balances on the interface after $t=0$, work done on both blocks are the same on amount, positive on one side and negative on the other. Energy gained on one side of the interface equals to energy lost on the other side. With conservation inside each block, total energy conserves during this procedure of interaction between blocks. This extends energy conservation from local level (i.e., inside the block) to global level (i.e., inter-block thus the whole field). Same is for momentum conservation.

§ 7 Ether Flow and Ether Motion

Applying (6.2) ~ (6.6), we can review a few special cases, which will be helpful for further discussions.

Case I: If at $t=0$, two adjacent blocks are both stationary but with different field strength, i.e., $v_1 = v_2 = 0$, $\Omega_1 \neq \Omega_2$ (Fig. 7-1), with (6.2) ~ (6.5) we have

$$\Omega' = \frac{1}{2}(\Omega_1 + \Omega_2), \quad \theta = \frac{\Omega_1 - \Omega_2}{\Omega_1 + \Omega_2} c, \quad \varepsilon_1 = -\frac{1}{2}(\Omega_1 - \Omega_2), \quad \varepsilon_2 = \frac{1}{2}(\Omega_1 - \Omega_2). \quad (7.1)$$

Note that the difference on original field strength is split into two perturbations, ε_1 and ε_2 , one positive and one negative, each has amplitude equals to half of the difference. Fields on both sides are averaged out when these perturbations spread out from the interface.

Fig. 7-1: Movement of interface with discontinuity in stationary field

The ether flows corresponding to ε_1 and ε_2 are $J_1 = \varepsilon_1 c$ and $J_2 = \varepsilon_2 c$, respectively, or in vector form, $\vec{J}_1 = \varepsilon_1 c \vec{e}_x$ and $\vec{J}_2 = \varepsilon_2 c \vec{e}_x$. Note that when $\Omega_1 > \Omega_2$ we have $\varepsilon_1 < 0$. In this case \vec{J}_1 is a negative perturbation, propagating to the left (i.e., $-\vec{e}_x$ direction).

Case II: If at $t=0$, $v_2=0$ and $\Omega_2 = \Omega_1(1 - \frac{v_1}{c})$, we have

$$\Omega' = \Omega_1, \theta = v_1, \varepsilon_1 = 0, \varepsilon_2 = \Omega_1 \frac{v_1}{c}. \quad (7.2)$$

In this case, the end state is exactly the same as original field on the left. This is the case of a perturbation $\varepsilon = \Omega \frac{v}{c}$ propagating in a stationary field Ω , which was discussed on § 2 (Fig. 2-1).

For field with speed v , if we formalistically divide the field strength Ω into two portions: static portion, ω_s , and dynamic portion, ω_d , as

$$\omega_s = \Omega(1 - \frac{v}{c}), \omega_d = \Omega \frac{v}{c}, \quad (7.3)$$

ether flow in the field can be calculated as $J_d = \omega_d c = \Omega v$. In other words, it can be considered as if the dynamic portion ω_d is moving in sound speed, and the static portion ω_s keeps stationary. For convenience purpose, we will call J_d “sound flow”, and call this analysis method “sound splitting” of ether field. It is a kinematically equivalent description of the moving field.

In the above case, the static portion on the left, ω_{s1} , equals to Ω_2 on the right. Kinematically speaking, we can consider that the sound flow passes through the interface without causing any change on the static portion.

In the cases that $\omega_{s1} \neq \Omega_2$, we can treat ω_{s1} and Ω_2 as two stationary block as in Case I, and add the two perturbations ε_1 and ε_2 with the original sound flow J_d . This gives the same results as (6.2) ~ (6.5).

Case III: Applying sound splitting to the general case in § 6, we can split field in the two blocks into four parts:

$$\omega_{s1} = \Omega_1(1 - \frac{v_1}{c}), \omega_{s2} = \Omega_2(1 - \frac{v_2}{c}) \text{ and } \omega_{d1} = \Omega_1 \frac{v_1}{c}, \omega_{d2} = \Omega_2 \frac{v_2}{c}. \quad (7.4)$$

Then treat ω_{s1} and ω_{s2} as two stationary blocks as in case I. If $\omega_{s1} \neq \omega_{s2}$, the difference will split into two perturbations:

$$\varepsilon_1, \varepsilon_2 = \pm \frac{1}{2}(\omega_{s1} - \omega_{s2}),$$

which bring two flows in $\pm \vec{e}_x$ directions:

$$\vec{J}_{\epsilon_1} = \epsilon_1 c \vec{e}_x, \quad \vec{J}_{\epsilon_2} = \epsilon_2 c \vec{e}_x.$$

With the sound flow in the original blocks

$$J_{d1} = \omega_{d1} c = \Omega_1 v_1, \quad J_{d2} = \omega_{d2} c = \Omega_2 v_2,$$

we have totally four flows. They can be combined in the way described below to calculate the field strength and speed in different area.

If two flows are on the same direction, they will both keep moving in sound speed, and the amplitudes add up in the overlap area. In the example shown in Fig. 7-2a, from the left to point A, the dynamic field is $\omega_d = \epsilon_1 + \epsilon_2$; Between A and B dynamic field is $\omega_d = \epsilon_1$; from point B to the right, there is no dynamic field. In all the areas, static field keeps no change from the original static field ω_{s0} . The actual field strength and speed can be calculated according to (7.3).

If two flows meet from opposite directions, we can also consider as if each of them keeps moving forward in sound speed, but in the overlapping area, part of the flows will stop each other and become static field. The difference of the two flows will form a new sound flow. In the example shown in Fig. 7-2b, two flows $J_1 = \epsilon_1 c$ and $J_2 = \epsilon_2 c$ from the left and right met each other. Assuming $\epsilon_2 \geq \epsilon_1$, in the area from the left to point A, dynamic field is $\omega_d = \epsilon_1$ and static field is $\omega_s = \omega_{s0}$; between A and B, $\omega_d = \epsilon_2 - \epsilon_1$, $\omega_s = 2\epsilon_1 + \omega_{s0}$; from B to the right, $\omega_d = \epsilon_2$, $\omega_s = \omega_{s0}$.

Fig. 7-2: Sound flows and combination

This is an equivalent (and intuitive) way to understand and calculate field status changes near an interface. The outcomes are the same as results using (6.2) ~ (6.6).

Case IV: For the general case in § 6, we can have another way to calculate the kinematically equivalent results.

Rewrite (6.2) and (6.3) as

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \Omega' c = \frac{1}{2}[(c + v_1)\Omega_1] + \frac{1}{2}[(c - v_2)\Omega_2] \\ \theta = \frac{\frac{1}{2}[(c + v_1)\Omega_1] - \frac{1}{2}[(c - v_2)\Omega_2]}{\frac{1}{2}[(c + v_1)\Omega_1] + \frac{1}{2}[(c - v_2)\Omega_2]} \end{array} \right. \quad (7.6)$$

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \theta = \frac{\frac{1}{2}[(c + v_1)\Omega_1] - \frac{1}{2}[(c - v_2)\Omega_2]}{\frac{1}{2}[(c + v_1)\Omega_1] + \frac{1}{2}[(c - v_2)\Omega_2]} \\ c = \frac{\frac{1}{2}[(c + v_1)\Omega_1] + \frac{1}{2}[(c - v_2)\Omega_2]}{\frac{1}{2}[(c + v_1)\Omega_1] + \frac{1}{2}[(c - v_2)\Omega_2]} \end{array} \right. \quad (7.7)$$

It seems like that the impacts of the two blocks to the interface are $\frac{1}{2}[(c + v_1)\Omega_1]$ and $\frac{1}{2}[(c - v_2)\Omega_2]$, respectively. In other words, for a field block Ω with velocity $\bar{v} = v\bar{e}_v$, the impacts on the “upstream” direction ($-\bar{e}_v$) and “downstream” direction (\bar{e}_v) can be measured by $\frac{1}{2}\Omega(c - v)$ and $\frac{1}{2}\Omega(c + v)$ respectively. These two properties are flow-like. If we define two flows, named up flow and down flow respectively, as

$$J_- = \frac{1}{2}\Omega(c - v), \quad J_+ = \frac{1}{2}\Omega(c + v), \quad (7.8)$$

and assume they both move in sound speed, we have

$$J_+ + J_- = \Omega c, \quad J_+ - J_- = \Omega v. \quad (7.9)$$

Then for the interface in § 6, we have four flows (J_{1+} , J_{1-} and J_{2+} , J_{2-} , shown in Fig. 7-3.), all in sound speed, interacting in the way described as in Case III. The field strength and speed in the settled area thus are

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \Omega' = \frac{1}{c}(J_{1+} + J_{2-}) \\ \theta = \frac{J_{1+} - J_{2-}}{J_{1+} + J_{2-}} c \end{array} \right.$$

which are the same as in (6.2) and (6.3).

Fig. 7-3: Sound flow split

In certain sense, the two flows, J_+ and J_- , describe the capability of a field block to expand in the downstream and upstream directions. In an extreme case that the block is placed in real empty space (i.e., $\Omega=0$ outside of the block), the block will expand in these two directions with flow of J_+ and J_- , respectively.

For convenient purpose, we will call this way of analysis “flow splitting”. Note that all the splitting analysis methods described in this section (i.e., sound splitting and flow splitting) are just kinematically equivalent ways to describe and calculate ether motions. They give the same results as the original formulas (6.2) ~ (6.6), which are derived from the basic assumptions, ECA and SPA.

From the splitting analysis, we can “extract” two special properties of a flow in the field. Firstly, the “wave front” of the flow is always moving in sound speed. Secondly, the flow density, as field strength multiplied by speed, keeps the same along the way, until it meets another flow in opposite direction and cancels each other (partly or totally). As a result of that, in the sense of kinematical equivalence, we can either consider all the ether in the field is moving in certain speed to support the flow, or only a portion of the ether (the dynamic portion) is moving in sound speed to provide the flow, as long as the product of speed and field strength remains the same. In the case that field strength changes along the way, the flow density will not change, but the actual speed of the field to support the flow will change accordingly.

Basically, these properties are still from ECA and SPA. They will be extended to three-dimensional cases in further discussion.

In previous discussions, we often examined a block of ether by “pushing” it on its sides, or “stopping” it on left or right. With flow splitting, we can now describe these procedures in a more intuitive way. For a block Ω with speed v , assuming v is from left to right, to push its left side to certain speed, what we need is to have the field outside of the interface at $t=0$ with same static field as in the block, and a dynamic field to provide the corresponding flow for the required speed. To “stop” the block from the left, we only need to have a stationary field outside on the left at $t=0$ with the same strength as the static portion in the block, i.e., $\Omega(1 - \frac{v}{c})$. On the right side, a stationary field with strength of

$\Omega(1 + \frac{v}{c})$ serves the same purpose.

As the “pushing” and “pulling” are done by flows reaching the interfaces at a time, movement of the interface starts immediately, and as long as the flows are steady, speed of the interface keeps steady.

In previous section, we also considered a Lagrangian surface as no ether passes through it. But in the sense of kinematical equivalence, it is the same as a surface with multiple flows passing through it and the “net flow” is zero. Flow analysis and Lagrangian/Eulerian interfaces are just for kinematical analysis. In the sense of field dynamics, in the actual cases each point in the field only has one velocity, which (by multiplying the field strength at that point) provides the net ether flow.

§8 Three-Dimensional Motions

The property that once generated, density of a sound flow will not change until it meets another sound flow in opposite direction, will be extended to three-dimensional cases, to explore energy and momentum conservation in field with three-dimensional motions and interactions.

The sound propagation assumption (SPA) also needs to be extended to three-dimensional cases. For one-dimensional motions, we assumed that perturbations (sounds) travel at a constant speed relative to the observer, regardless of motion status of the field in which perturbations are traveling. We will further assume that this applies to the cases that velocity of the field is not in parallel to the propagating direction of the perturbation. In other words, sound speed in ether field is not impacted by either the longitudinal or the lateral speed of the field.

Consider a uniform block of field with strength of Ω and velocity of $\vec{v} = v_x \vec{e}_x + v_y \vec{e}_y + v_z \vec{e}_z$. Recall the energy and pressure definitions, (4.1) and (5.2). Total energy and pressure should not change when coordinate system change directions. So they are still $E = (1 + \frac{v^2}{c^2})\Omega^2 V$ and $P = (1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2})\Omega^2$.

For convenience, we can combine v_y and v_z to a lateral speed v_\perp as $v_\perp^2 = v_y^2 + v_z^2$, and rewrite the velocity as $\vec{v} = v_x \vec{e}_x + v_\perp \vec{e}_\perp$. Accordingly, the sound flow can be split as $\vec{J} = \Omega v_x \vec{e}_x + \Omega v_\perp \vec{e}_\perp = \vec{J}_x + \vec{J}_\perp$.

Consider all the sides of the block as Lagrangian surfaces and assume that at $t=0$, the block is pushed/pulled to stop in x direction from both of its sides in x . Similar to the discussion on §4, two perturbations, $\varepsilon = \pm \frac{v_x}{c} \Omega$, will start from both sides in x and move towards the center of the block. In the lateral direction \vec{e}_\perp , the field will keep uniform and keep moving with the unchanged flow density J_\perp . To maintain this flow density, when field strength change, speed in \vec{e}_\perp will change accordingly.

Fig. 8-1: A field block with initial lateral speed being blocked to stop

At $t = L/(2c)$, the two perturbations meet at the center of the block in x direction. The field strength of the left half (Ω'_1) and the right half (Ω'_2) are now

$$\Omega'_1 = \Omega - \varepsilon = \Omega\left(1 - \frac{v_x}{c}\right), \quad \Omega'_2 = \Omega + \varepsilon = \Omega\left(1 + \frac{v_x}{c}\right).$$

At this point of time, speed in x direction is zero for the whole block. Speed in \bar{e}_\perp direction, $v'_{\perp 1}$ (on the left half) and $v'_{\perp 2}$ (on the right half), can be calculated from the unchanged flow density $J_\perp = \Omega v_\perp$ and new field strength Ω'_1 and Ω'_2 . That gives

$$v'_{\perp 1} = \frac{v_\perp}{1 - \frac{v_x}{c}} \quad \text{and} \quad v'_{\perp 2} = \frac{v_\perp}{1 + \frac{v_x}{c}}.$$

Assuming $v_x > 0$, we obviously have $\Omega'_1 < \Omega < \Omega'_2$ and $v'_{\perp 1} > v_\perp > v'_{\perp 2}$ (and $\Omega'_1 v'_{\perp 1} = \Omega v_\perp = \Omega'_2 v'_{\perp 2}$). In other words, on the left half, when the perturbation passes by, speed in x direction becomes zero; field strength decreases from Ω to Ω'_1 ; and the lateral speed increases from v_\perp to $v'_{\perp 1}$. At different locations in x , lateral speed increases at different time. The left-most part speeds up first when the perturbation starts from there, then other parts along x direction speed up in sequence. As a result of that, if the initial block is in cuboid shape, the left half will become a parallelepiped (parallelogram in the top-down view, as shown in Fig. 8.2(c)). The volume however keeps the same as in the initial block. Similar procedure happens on the right half of the block. There the lateral speed decreases from v_\perp to $v'_{\perp 2}$ when the perturbation sweeps from right towards the block center, and the shape changes to a parallelepiped as well (Fig. 8.2(c)).

Fig. 8-2: "top-down view" of a block with initial lateral speed being blocked to stop in x

After $t=0$, sides in x direction stay steady in x direction, thus no work is done to the block in this direction. In \bar{e}_\perp direction, the $+\bar{e}_\perp$ side and $-\bar{e}_\perp$ side (i.e., the upstream side and the downstream side) have the same pressure and speed all the time. Net work done to the block by these sides is also zero.

At $t= L/(2c)$, applying (4.1), we can calculate energy on the left half and the right half and add them together. That gives

$$E = \frac{V}{2} \left(1 + \frac{v'_{\perp 1}{}^2}{c^2}\right) \Omega_1'^2 + \frac{V}{2} \left(1 + \frac{v'_{\perp 2}{}^2}{c^2}\right) \Omega_2'^2 = \left(1 + \frac{v_x^2 + v_\perp^2}{c^2}\right) \Omega^2 V = \left(1 + \frac{v^2}{c^2}\right) \Omega^2 V$$

which is the same as energy of the initial block.

It is also straightforward to confirm that energy keeps the same at any moment when $0 < t < L/(2c)$.

For momentum, in \bar{e}_x direction, after $t=0$, the pressure on both sides are respectively

$$P_{x-} = \left(1 - \frac{v'_{\perp 1}{}^2}{c^2}\right) \Omega_1'^2 \quad \text{and} \quad P_{x+} = \left(1 - \frac{v'_{\perp 2}{}^2}{c^2}\right) \Omega_2'^2.$$

It can be calculated that change of momentum equal to difference of impulses in \bar{e}_x direction.

In \bar{e}_\perp direction, as pressures on both sides are equal all the time, net impulse to the block is zero. Momentum can be calculated from Ω_1' , Ω_2' and $v'_{\perp 1}$, $v'_{\perp 2}$. It remains the same as in the initial block.

Applying similar analysis to the case that a block with speed in \bar{e}_\perp direction is accelerated/decelerated in \bar{e}_x direction, it can be confirmed that energy conservation stands, and momentum conserves in each direction of \bar{e}_x and \bar{e}_\perp .

Same as in one-dimensional cases, for a Lagrangian interface to be steady, normal speed and pressure need to be the same on both sides. In three-dimensional cases, if speed in tangential direction is not the same on different sides of an interface, it is possible to have different field strength on different sides while pressure is still balancing.

As pressure is the same on both sides, when a Lagrangian interface moves, work done on one side equals to work done on the other. This means energy can transfer through interfaces without gain/loss in the three-dimensional cases, and the total energy conserves. Same is for momentum.

§9 Ether Field Equations

Apparently, ether is quite similar to ideal gas: compressible, following momentum and energy conservations. On the other hand, for ether field, pressure and energy density are known functions of field strength and velocity. This greatly simplifies the “constitutive relation”. Another special property of ether compared to gases is that mass does not conserve. Ether conserves, instead.

Split the field to volume elements, and apply ether, momentum and energy conservations to the elements, we can derive three basic equations in a way similar to the derivation of Navier-Stokes equations in fluid mechanics.

The three equations, named ether equation, momentum equation and energy equation respectively hereafter in this paper, are

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \Omega + \nabla \cdot (\Omega \bar{u}) = 0 \\ \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \left(\frac{2\Omega^2}{c^2} \bar{u} \right) + \nabla \cdot \left(\frac{2\Omega^2}{c^2} \bar{u} \bar{u} \right) = -\nabla \cdot \left(\left(1 - \frac{u^2}{c^2}\right) \Omega^2 \right) \\ \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \left(\left(1 + \frac{u^2}{c^2}\right) \Omega^2 \right) + \nabla \cdot \left(\left(1 + \frac{u^2}{c^2}\right) \Omega^2 \bar{u} \right) = -\nabla \cdot \left(\left(1 - \frac{u^2}{c^2}\right) \Omega^2 \bar{u} \right) \end{array} \right. \quad \begin{array}{l} (9.1) \\ (9.2) \\ (9.3) \end{array}$$

Actually, the ether equation was also given on §1 as (1.1), as a direct conclusion of ECA. Momentum equation and the energy equation are based on the definitions of momentum and energy in §4 and the related conservation properties derived in previous sections.

As an alternative format, energy equation (9.3) can be simplified to

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t} \left(\left(1 + \frac{u^2}{c^2}\right) \Omega^2 \right) + 2\nabla \cdot (\Omega^2 \bar{u}) = 0.$$

As the only unknowns here are field strength and velocity, these three equations, as a system, are overdetermined. However, they are consistent, as shown below.

Expand (9.2) as

$$\Omega^2 \frac{\partial \bar{u}}{\partial t} + \bar{u} \frac{\partial \Omega^2}{\partial t} + \Omega^2 \bar{u} \cdot \nabla \bar{u} + \Omega^2 \bar{u} \nabla \cdot \bar{u} + \bar{u} (\bar{u} \cdot \nabla \Omega^2) = -\frac{1}{2} \nabla \cdot ((c^2 - u^2) \Omega^2),$$

dot-multiply both sides by velocity, and apply the identity of $\bar{u} \cdot (\bar{u} \cdot \nabla \bar{u}) = \frac{1}{2} \bar{u} \cdot \nabla u^2$, we have

$$\Omega^2 \frac{\partial u^2}{\partial t} + 2u^2 \frac{\partial \Omega^2}{\partial t} + \Omega^2 \bar{u} \cdot \nabla u^2 + 2\Omega^2 u^2 \nabla \cdot \bar{u} + 2u^2 (\bar{u} \cdot \nabla \Omega^2) = -\bar{u} \cdot \nabla ((c^2 - u^2) \Omega^2). \quad (9.4)$$

Multiply (9.1) by $2c^2 \Omega$, we get

$$c^2 \frac{\partial \Omega^2}{\partial t} + 2c^2 \Omega^2 \nabla \cdot \bar{u} + c^2 \bar{u} \cdot \nabla \Omega^2 = 0. \quad (9.5)$$

Add (9.5) to (9.4), and make use of (9.1) again to simply the result, we have

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t} \left((c^2 + u^2) \Omega^2 \right) + u^2 (\bar{u} \cdot \nabla \Omega^2) + \Omega^2 \bar{u} \cdot \nabla u^2 + 2c^2 \Omega^2 \nabla \cdot \bar{u} + c^2 \bar{u} \cdot \nabla \Omega^2 = -\bar{u} \cdot \nabla \left((c^2 - u^2) \Omega^2 \right)$$

$$\text{or } \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \left((c^2 + u^2) \Omega^2 \right) + \Omega^2 \bar{u} \cdot \nabla (c^2 + u^2) + (c^2 + u^2) \nabla \cdot (\Omega^2 \bar{u}) = -(c^2 - u^2) \Omega^2 \nabla \cdot \bar{u} - \bar{u} \cdot \nabla \left((c^2 - u^2) \Omega^2 \right)$$

which is just the energy equation (9.3).

In other words, energy equation can be derived from ether equation and momentum equation. In this sense, energy conservation can be considered as a consequence of ether and momentum conservations.

Recall that energy and momentum conservations were derived from the same sound propagation procedure. They co-exist in the same procedure, and are both results of SPA and ECA. It is not a surprise that they are not independent (and are consistent).

As a result of that, we can take away the energy equation from the system (and use it as a derived equation if need). This leaves the ether equation and the momentum equation to form a closed equation system:

$$\begin{cases} \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \Omega + \nabla \cdot (\Omega \bar{u}) = 0 & (9.1) \\ \frac{\partial}{\partial t} (\Omega^2 \bar{u}) + \nabla \cdot (\Omega^2 \bar{u} \bar{u}) = -\frac{c^2}{2} \nabla \cdot \left(\left(1 - \frac{u^2}{c^2} \right) \Omega^2 \right) & (9.2) \end{cases}$$

This is the fundamental equation system for ether field. In the following sections, we will concentrate on the properties of this system and the possible solutions.

§10 Background Field

According to SPA, ether will diffuse from high pressure regions to low pressure regions. Unless moving in sound speed (thus pressure is zero), field in an area can not stay stable if surrounded by empty space (i.e., space with zero field strength). For any structure (formed by stationary field or field moving slower than sound speed) to stably exist, there must be a non-zero field in the background, to provide positive pressure as the “boundary conditions”. Field structures may then exist in low-pressure regions inside this background field, balanced by certain kind of motions.

We will assume the existence of such a background field (and call it BGF in short). It suffuses throughout the whole space.

This actually sketches a picture of the universe, from the ether field point of view. Ether, as the only being in the universe, permeates throughout the space. Ununiformities cause motions. Motions can cause field redistributions (and ununiformities). i.e., motion and ununiformity are reciprocal causation. Some motions appear as perturbations (sounds), propagating through the field in a fix speed. Some

motions (e.g., central motions) may exist within a region in the field. This kind of motion structures, if steady and with certain stable properties, form particles. All the field structures (including the background field) follow the same basic equations. This is primarily the simple model of universe this paper is attempting to build.

Here “field structures” refer to those regions where field strength and velocity are forming certain stable patterns. We will also call development and interaction of field structures as “procedures” or “events”. However, there is no clear distinction between field structures and the background field. Ether field, existing in the whole space, acts as a whole following the same equations in all the places, all the time. Background field is not necessarily uniform or steady. Instead, there can be all kinds of distributions and motions. We can extract stable patterns as “field structures” or particles for particular interest. But in principle, background field, all the structures, interactions and events could be described by solving the field equations under certain initial/boundary conditions.

On the other hand, the equations and the description of the field are based on certain measurement systems. In this picture of universe, ether is what it is, acts as how it acts. The measurement systems are artificial (defined by human). Measurement results depend on many factors (e.g., scope of the measurement, motion status of the observer), and every observer relies on the measurement results to describe and understand the field. So different observers can have different descriptions for the same field and events. Moreover, as ether is the only being in the space, there are no other objects to reference to when doing measurements. What can be employed to measure the field is the field itself. Strictly speaking, clocks and rulers are just certain field structures, which follow the same equations as do other parts of the field. Clocks and rulers are used to measure.

As a result of that, measurements have limitations. Certain properties are the same for all observers (i.e., are absolute). Others can be different when measured by different observers (i.e., are relative). The relative properties may also follow certain rules of transformation between different observers’ views.

There are also properties that are fundamentally not detectable (not measureable). One example is the (absolute) field strength. The basic field equations are homogeneous in Ω . If (Ω, u_x, u_y, u_z) is a solution to the equations, $(k\Omega, u_x, u_y, u_z)$ is also a solution (when k is a positive constant and field strength in the boundary/initial conditions are also multiplied by k). This means, an observer inside certain boundary can only measure relative field strength inside the boundary. Absolute strength is not measureable, as absolute strength of the field does not have any impact on the physics laws the observed procedures follow.

We will call this “strength relativity” of ether field.

§11 Motion Relativity and Lorentz Transformation

As basic assumptions/postulates, ECA and SPA are universal. They are assumed to stand regardless of strength, uniformity and motion status of the field, regardless of motion status of the observer. From different observers’ views, space (distance between events, size of field structures, etc.),

time (duration between events) and field strength, velocity, etc., can be different even for the same field and events. However, these properties always follow ECA and SPA. In principle, ECA and SPA can be considered as basic requirements to a measurement system (i.e., reference system) in the field.

As ECA and SPA always stand, so do the ether field equations, which are derived from ECA and SPA. This is regardless of motion status of observers. In other words, motion status of an observer (reference system) does not impact the physics laws the observed procedures satisfy.

This is another relative property of the field. We will call it “motion relativity” hereafter in this paper.

In an obvious sense, this is the “ether version” of the (special and general) principle of relativity that Albert Einstein introduced about a century ago to build special and general theory of relativities^{[9], [10]}. However, it is slightly different on the approach towards this principle here. In Einstein’s theories, principle of relativity is a postulate independent to light speed constancy. Here in ether field theory, we set sound (light) speed constancy as a postulate (SPA), which together with another postulate (ECA) leads to momentum and energy conservations and the basic field equations. As ether is assumed to be the only being in the space, the field equation system determines all physics procedures, or in other words, contains all the physics laws. Wherever SPA and ECA stand (regardless of inertial or accelerating reference system), the equations apply and physics laws stand the same.

In this sense, special and general principles of relativity are “included” in motion relativity. As consequences, the ether field theory is “relativistic”. As will be discussed in rest of this section, the field equations are consistent with Lorentz transformation. On the other hand, there is a gravity-like force in the field, which can be considered as effect of ununiformity of motion over space. This force term is always balanced by a term in the acceleration. (See discussion in next section). With these, loosely speaking it can be considered that special and general theories of relativity are essentially included in ether field theory.

Let us consider two different observers (reference systems), O and O’, in the same region of the field. O can be in arbitrary motion status but O’ relative to O moves in a steady velocity, \bar{v} ($|\bar{v}| < c$). Obviously, each of O and O’ will have particular measurement/observation of the background field and the field structures/events. But for both of them, SPA and ECA stand. Perturbations (sounds) travel in the same fix speed relative to each of them, and observations of the field from each observer respectively satisfy the basic equations.

From light speed constancy and principle of relativity, Einstein derived Lorentz transformations, which describe the relations between time and space measured from different (inertial) reference systems. If we let sound speed take the position of light speed, we are in a similar situation and can do similar derivation that leads to an ether version of Lorentz transformations (in which light speed is replaced by sound speed).

We would thus expect that the transformations are consistent with the field equations. Or in other words, the field equations should be Lorentz-invariant. This is actually true, as shown below in this section.

For convenience, let us consider the standard configuration in which origin points of reference systems $O(x, y, z, t)$ and $O'(x', y', z', t')$ are coincident at $t=0$, x and x' align, y and y' , z and z' are parallel respectively, and the velocity of O' relative to O (denoted as \bar{v}) is in x direction. Field strength and speed measured from the two reference systems are respectively denoted as (Ω, u_x, u_y, u_z) and

$(\Omega', u'_x, u'_y, u'_z)$. With Lorentz factor $\alpha \triangleq \sqrt{1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2}}$, the Lorentz transformations read

$$x' = \frac{1}{\alpha}(x - vt), \quad y' = y, \quad z' = z, \quad t' = \frac{1}{\alpha}\left(t - \frac{vx}{c^2}\right)$$

or
$$x = \frac{1}{\alpha}(x' + vt'), \quad y = y', \quad z = z', \quad t = \frac{1}{\alpha}\left(t' + \frac{vx'}{c^2}\right)$$

and
$$\frac{\partial}{\partial x} = \frac{1}{\alpha} \frac{\partial}{\partial x'} - \frac{1}{\alpha} \frac{v}{c^2} \frac{\partial}{\partial t'}, \quad \frac{\partial}{\partial y} = \frac{\partial}{\partial y'}, \quad \frac{\partial}{\partial z} = \frac{\partial}{\partial z'}, \quad \frac{\partial}{\partial t} = \frac{1}{\alpha} \frac{\partial}{\partial t'} - \frac{v}{\alpha} \frac{\partial}{\partial x'},$$

hence

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} u'_x = \frac{(u_x - v)}{1 - \frac{u_x v}{c^2}} \\ u'_y = \frac{\alpha u_y}{1 - \frac{u_x v}{c^2}} \\ u'_z = \frac{\alpha u_z}{1 - \frac{u_x v}{c^2}} \\ \Omega' = \frac{\Omega}{\alpha} \left(1 - \frac{u_x v}{c^2}\right) \end{array} \right. \quad \text{or} \quad \left\{ \begin{array}{l} u_x = \frac{(u'_x + v)}{1 + \frac{u'_x v}{c^2}} \\ u_y = \frac{\alpha u'_y}{1 + \frac{u'_x v}{c^2}} \\ u_z = \frac{\alpha u'_z}{1 + \frac{u'_x v}{c^2}} \\ \Omega = \frac{\Omega'}{\alpha} \left(1 + \frac{u'_x v}{c^2}\right) \end{array} \right.$$

Note: transformation of field strength can be derived from ECA and the transformation of dimensions (volumes).

Substitute the transformations to ether question (9.1), we have

$$\frac{1}{\alpha} \frac{\partial}{\partial t'} \Omega - \frac{v}{\alpha} \frac{\partial}{\partial x'} \Omega + \frac{1}{\alpha} \frac{\partial}{\partial x'} (\Omega u_x) - \frac{1}{\alpha} \frac{v}{c^2} \frac{\partial}{\partial t'} (\Omega u_x) + \frac{\partial}{\partial y'} (\Omega u_y) + \frac{\partial}{\partial z'} (\Omega u_z) = 0$$

or
$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t'} \left(\frac{\Omega}{\alpha} \left(1 - \frac{vu_x}{c^2}\right) \right) + \frac{\partial}{\partial x'} \left(\frac{\Omega}{\alpha} (u_x - v) \right) + \frac{\partial}{\partial y'} (\Omega u_y) + \frac{\partial}{\partial z'} (\Omega u_z) = 0$$

which is

$$\frac{\partial \Omega'}{\partial t'} + \frac{\partial}{\partial x'} \left(\frac{\Omega'(u_x - v)}{1 - \frac{u_x v}{c^2}} \right) + \frac{\partial}{\partial y'} \left(\frac{\alpha \Omega' u_y}{1 - \frac{u_x v}{c^2}} \right) + \frac{\partial}{\partial z'} \left(\frac{\alpha \Omega' u_z}{1 - \frac{u_x v}{c^2}} \right) = 0$$

or

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t'} \Omega' + \frac{\partial}{\partial x'} (\Omega' u'_x) + \frac{\partial}{\partial y'} (\Omega' u'_y) + \frac{\partial}{\partial z'} (\Omega' u'_z) = 0.$$

This is the ether question in $O'(x', y', z', t')$. In other words, the ether equation is Lorentz-invariant.

It is also straightforward to confirm that pressure is Lorentz-invariant. i.e.,

$$\Omega^2 (c^2 - u^2) = \Omega'^2 (c^2 - u'^2).$$

With Lorentz-invariance of pressure, momentum equations in y and z direction can be transformed similar to the ether equation. Taking y direction as an example, the momentum equation

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t} (\Omega^2 u_y) + \frac{\partial}{\partial x} (\Omega^2 u_y u_x) + \frac{\partial}{\partial y} (\Omega^2 u_y u_y) + \frac{\partial}{\partial z} (\Omega^2 u_y u_z) = -\frac{1}{2} \frac{\partial}{\partial y} (\Omega^2 (c^2 - u^2))$$

is also

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t'} \left(\frac{\Omega'^2 u_y}{\alpha} \left(1 - \frac{v u_x}{c^2} \right) \right) + \frac{\partial}{\partial x'} \left(\frac{\Omega'^2 u_y}{\alpha} (u_x - v) \right) + \frac{\partial}{\partial y'} (\Omega'^2 u'_y u'_y) + \frac{\partial}{\partial z'} (\Omega'^2 u'_y u'_z) = -\frac{1}{2} \frac{\partial}{\partial y'} (\Omega'^2 (c^2 - u'^2))$$

or

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t'} (\Omega'^2 u'_y) + \frac{\partial}{\partial x'} (\Omega'^2 u'_x u'_y) + \frac{\partial}{\partial y'} (\Omega'^2 u'_y u'_y) + \frac{\partial}{\partial z'} (\Omega'^2 u'_y u'_z) = -\frac{1}{2} \frac{\partial}{\partial y'} (\Omega'^2 (c^2 - u'^2))$$

which is exactly the momentum equation in y' direction for $O'(x', y', z', t')$.

Similar procedure applies to the energy equation as well. It transforms the energy equation (9.3) from $O(x, y, z, t)$ as

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t} \left(\left(1 + \frac{u^2}{c^2} \right) \Omega^2 \right) + \nabla \cdot \left(\left(1 + \frac{u^2}{c^2} \right) \Omega^2 \vec{u} \right) = -\nabla \cdot \left(\left(1 - \frac{u^2}{c^2} \right) \Omega^2 \vec{u} \right)$$

to $O'(x', y', z', t')$ as

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t'} \left(\left(1 + \frac{u'^2}{c^2} \right) \Omega'^2 \right) + \nabla' \cdot \left(\left(1 + \frac{u'^2}{c^2} \right) \Omega'^2 \vec{u}' \right) = -\nabla' \cdot \left(\left(1 - \frac{u'^2}{c^2} \right) \Omega'^2 \vec{u}' \right)$$

In x direction, the momentum equation is

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t}(\Omega^2 u_x) + \frac{\partial}{\partial x}(\Omega^2 u_x^2) + \frac{\partial}{\partial y}(\Omega^2 u_x u_y) + \frac{\partial}{\partial z}(\Omega^2 u_x u_z) = -\frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left(\Omega^2 \frac{c^2 - u_x^2 - u_y^2 - u_z^2}{2} \right).$$

The left-hand side can be transformed to

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{1}{\alpha} \frac{\partial}{\partial t'}(\Omega^2 u_x) - \frac{v}{\alpha} \frac{\partial}{\partial x'}(\Omega^2 u_x) + \frac{1}{\alpha} \frac{\partial}{\partial x'}(\Omega^2 u_x^2) - \frac{1}{\alpha} \frac{v}{c^2} \frac{\partial}{\partial t'}(\Omega^2 u_x^2) + \frac{\partial}{\partial y'}(\Omega^2 u_x u_y) + \frac{\partial}{\partial z'}(\Omega^2 u_x u_z) \\ &= \frac{\partial}{\partial t'} \left(\Omega^2 \frac{u_x}{\alpha} \frac{c^2 - v u_x}{c^2} \right) + \frac{\partial}{\partial x'} \left(\Omega^2 \frac{u_x}{\alpha} (u_x - v) \right) + \frac{\partial}{\partial y'}(\Omega^2 u_x u_y) + \frac{\partial}{\partial z'}(\Omega^2 u_x u_z) \\ &= \frac{\partial}{\partial t'} \left(\Omega'^2 \frac{\alpha^2}{\left(1 - \frac{v u_x}{c^2}\right)^2} \frac{u_x}{\alpha} \frac{c^2 - v u_x}{c^2} \right) + \frac{\partial}{\partial x'} \left(\Omega'^2 \frac{\alpha^2}{\left(1 - \frac{v u_x}{c^2}\right)^2} \frac{u_x}{\alpha} (u_x - v) \right) \\ & \quad + \frac{\partial}{\partial y'} \left(\Omega'^2 \frac{\alpha^2}{\left(1 - \frac{v u_x}{c^2}\right)^2} u_x u_y \right) + \frac{\partial}{\partial z'} \left(\Omega'^2 \frac{\alpha^2}{\left(1 - \frac{v u_x}{c^2}\right)^2} u_x u_z \right) \\ &= \frac{\partial}{\partial t'} \left(\Omega'^2 \frac{\alpha u_x}{1 - \frac{v u_x}{c^2}} \right) + \frac{\partial}{\partial x'} \left(\Omega'^2 \frac{\alpha u_x}{1 - \frac{v u_x}{c^2}} \frac{u_x - v}{1 - \frac{v u_x}{c^2}} \right) + \frac{\partial}{\partial y'} \left(\Omega'^2 \frac{\alpha u_x}{1 - \frac{v u_x}{c^2}} \frac{\alpha u_y}{1 - \frac{v u_x}{c^2}} \right) + \frac{\partial}{\partial z'} \left(\Omega'^2 \frac{\alpha u_x}{1 - \frac{v u_x}{c^2}} \frac{\alpha u_z}{1 - \frac{v u_x}{c^2}} \right) \end{aligned}$$

and the right-hand side is

$$\begin{aligned} & -\frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left(\Omega^2 \frac{c^2 - u_x^2 - u_y^2 - u_z^2}{2} \right) = -\frac{1}{\alpha} \frac{\partial}{\partial x'} \left(\Omega^2 \frac{c^2 - u_x^2 - u_y^2 - u_z^2}{2} \right) + \frac{1}{\alpha} \frac{v}{c^2} \frac{\partial}{\partial t'} \left(\Omega^2 \frac{c^2 - u_x^2 - u_y^2 - u_z^2}{2} \right) \\ &= -\frac{1}{\alpha} \frac{\partial}{\partial x'} \left(\Omega'^2 \frac{c^2 - u_x'^2 - u_y'^2 - u_z'^2}{2} \right) + \frac{1}{\alpha} \frac{v}{c^2} \frac{\partial}{\partial t'} \left(\Omega'^2 \frac{c^2 - u_x'^2 - u_y'^2 - u_z'^2}{2} \right) \end{aligned}$$

Multiple both sides by α , and apply the identity of $\frac{\alpha^2 u_x}{1 - \frac{v u_x}{c^2}} = \frac{u_x - v}{1 - \frac{v u_x}{c^2}} + v$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{\partial}{\partial t'} \left(\Omega'^2 \left(\frac{(u_x - v)}{1 - \frac{v u_x}{c^2}} + v - \frac{v c^2 - v u_x'^2 - v u_y'^2 - v u_z'^2}{2 c^2} \right) \right) + \frac{\partial}{\partial x'} \left(\Omega'^2 \frac{(u_x - v)}{1 - \frac{v u_x}{c^2}} \frac{u_x - v}{1 - \frac{v u_x}{c^2}} + \Omega'^2 v \frac{u_x - v}{1 - \frac{v u_x}{c^2}} \right) \\ & + \frac{\partial}{\partial y'} \left(\Omega'^2 \frac{(u_x - v)}{1 - \frac{v u_x}{c^2}} \frac{\alpha u_y}{1 - \frac{v u_x}{c^2}} + \Omega'^2 v \frac{\alpha u_y}{1 - \frac{v u_x}{c^2}} \right) + \frac{\partial}{\partial z'} \left(\Omega'^2 \frac{(u_x - v)}{1 - \frac{v u_x}{c^2}} \frac{\alpha u_z}{1 - \frac{v u_x}{c^2}} + \Omega'^2 v \frac{\alpha u_z}{1 - \frac{v u_x}{c^2}} \right) = -\frac{\partial}{\partial x'} \left(\Omega'^2 \frac{c^2 - u'^2}{2} \right) \end{aligned}$$

or

$$\begin{aligned}
& \frac{\partial}{\partial t'}(\Omega'^2 u'_x) + \frac{\partial}{\partial x'}(\Omega'^2 u'^2_x) + \frac{\partial}{\partial y'}(\Omega'^2 u'_x u'_y) + \frac{\partial}{\partial z'}(\Omega'^2 u'_x u'_z) + \frac{\partial}{\partial x'}(\Omega'^2 v u'_x) + \frac{\partial}{\partial y'}(\Omega'^2 v u'_y) + \frac{\partial}{\partial z'}(\Omega'^2 v u'_z) \\
&= -\frac{\partial}{\partial x'}\left(\Omega'^2 \frac{c^2 - u'^2}{2}\right) - \frac{\partial}{\partial t'}\left(\Omega'^2 v \left(\frac{c^2 + u'^2_x + u'^2_y + u'^2_z}{2c^2}\right)\right)
\end{aligned}$$

Subtract the energy equation from the above, we have

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t'}(\Omega'^2 u'_x) + \frac{\partial}{\partial x'}(\Omega'^2 u'^2_x) + \frac{\partial}{\partial y'}(\Omega'^2 u'_x u'_y) + \frac{\partial}{\partial z'}(\Omega'^2 u'_x u'_z) = -\frac{\partial}{\partial x'}\left(\Omega'^2 \frac{c^2 - u'^2}{2}\right)$$

which is the momentum equation in x' direction for $O'(x', y', z', t')$.

This closes the proof of Lorentz-invariance of all the equations (under the standard configuration).

Existence of ether does not necessarily lead to absolute space/time. In the ether model proposed in this paper, based on ECA and SPA, the field equation system by its nature is Lorentz-invariant. This means that time and space are relative in the proposed ether field. From different reference systems that are moving in steady velocity relative to each other, measurements/descriptions of the field follow Lorentz-transformations and satisfy the same equations. In other words, Lorentz transformations are primarily implied in the ether field equations. As a result, solutions of the equation system are also Lorentz-invariant, thus are consistent with special relativity theory. In this sense, it can be considered that ether field theory, based on ECA and SPA, organically implies special relativity.

§12 Ununiform Motions and Gravity-like Force

Even with the background field throughout the space, the concept of inertial reference system is only for multiple systems that each is moving in steady velocity relative to each of others. For a single reference system in the field, it is not possible (and not necessary) to know whether it is an inertial system or an accelerating one. For example, from a certain reference system A, field in a region may be flat (i.e., with uniform strength and uniform/steady velocity). But from another system B (that is not in steady velocity relative to A), field in this region can be non-flat. Even in this special case, the observation from A and that from B are equivalent, as we do not know whether the field is “indeed” flat or not without employing a reference system. System A is not special to be considered as an inertial one (even though it is “following the field” in certain sense). Neither is system B.

In general, the observations from system A and from system B could have complicated relation. However, according to motion relativity, they all follow ECA and SPA, thus follow the same equations. By further analyzing the equations, we may find some clues to the relation.

In particular, pressure is a function of field strength and speed, while force density is gradient of pressure. Obviously, force could be different for different observers. On the other hand, momentum equation requires that total force equals to change rate of momentum. The difference of forces from different reference systems should be reflected in the momentum equation.

Expanding both sides of momentum equation (9.2) and applying the identity of

$$\vec{V} \cdot \nabla \vec{V} = \frac{1}{2} \nabla V^2 - \vec{V} \times (\nabla \times \vec{V}),$$

we have

$$\frac{2\Omega}{c^2} \frac{\partial}{\partial t} (\Omega \bar{u}) + \frac{2\Omega \bar{u}}{c^2} \frac{\partial \Omega}{\partial t} + \frac{2}{c^2} (\nabla \cdot (\Omega \bar{u})) (\Omega \bar{u}) - \frac{2}{c^2} (\Omega \bar{u}) \times (\nabla \times (\Omega \bar{u})) + \nabla \frac{\Omega^2 u^2}{c^2} = \nabla \frac{\Omega^2 u^2}{c^2} - \nabla \Omega^2$$

or

$$\frac{2\Omega}{c^2} \frac{\partial}{\partial t} (\Omega \bar{u}) + \frac{2\Omega \bar{u}}{c^2} \left[\frac{\partial \Omega}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (\Omega \bar{u}) \right] - \frac{2}{c^2} (\Omega \bar{u}) \times (\nabla \times (\Omega \bar{u})) + \nabla \frac{\Omega^2 u^2}{c^2} = \nabla \frac{\Omega^2 u^2}{c^2} - \nabla \Omega^2.$$

The second term vanishes according to the ether equation. Thus we have

$$\frac{2\Omega}{c^2} \frac{\partial}{\partial t} (\Omega \bar{u}) - \frac{2}{c^2} (\Omega \bar{u}) \times (\nabla \times (\Omega \bar{u})) + \nabla \frac{\Omega^2 u^2}{c^2} = \nabla \frac{\Omega^2 u^2}{c^2} - \nabla \Omega^2 \quad (12.1)$$

or

$$\frac{2\Omega}{c^2} \frac{\partial}{\partial t} (\Omega \bar{u}) - \frac{2}{c^2} (\Omega \bar{u}) \times (\nabla \times (\Omega \bar{u})) = -\nabla \Omega^2 \quad (12.2)$$

There is a common term, $\nabla \frac{\Omega^2 u^2}{c^2}$ (denoted as \vec{G} hereafter for convenience) on both sides of (12.1).

But on different sides, this term is from different source.

On the right-hand side of (12.1), the two terms represent two parts of pressure gradient, or two sources of force. They can be considered as force due to ununiformity of kinetic energy density and static energy density, respectively. These two terms together represent all the forces apply to ether in the field.

On the left-hand side of (12.1), \vec{G} is part of the momentum change rate. If we consider $\vec{A} = \Omega \bar{u}$ as ether flow in the field, $\vec{G} = \nabla \frac{\Omega^2 u^2}{c^2} = \nabla \frac{A^2}{c^2}$ is gradient of ether flow density (square). It can be considered as momentum change caused by ununiform motion, or momentum change rate (over time) due to momentum flow change over space. The other two terms on the left-hand side can be considered as local momentum change rate over time and momentum change rate due to rotation, respectively. These three terms together form the total momentum change rate, which equals to total force according to momentum equation.

As \vec{G} appears on both sides of the equation, it cancels itself. In other words, the momentum change caused by ununiform motion is always balanced by the force due to ununiform kinetic energy. The momentum equation thus becomes (12.2). However, when we calculate the total force, this term is always part of it. Same is for total acceleration (total momentum change rate, as on the left-hand side of (12.1)).

$\frac{\Omega^2 u^2}{c^2}$ is non-negative and is proportional to square of speed. At the points where field speed is zero, $\frac{\Omega^2 u^2}{c^2}$ reaches the minimum and \vec{G} vanishes. Equivalently speaking, at any point in the field, from a local body-following reference system, ether speed is zero and this gradient term vanishes.

In other words, as a force term, \vec{G} can be locally vanished by choosing proper reference system. This is similar to the feature of gravity (which is balanced out by inertia force in a free-falling reference system). In this sense, this force term \vec{G} is similar to gravity in certain degree. We will call \vec{G} a “gravity-like” force, or “ether-Gravity” (or “e-Gravity” in short) hereafter in this paper. The prefix “e” indicates that it is in ether field level, rather than in particle level as our normal understanding for gravity.

In general relativity, gravity is considered property of space (i.e., curvature of spacetime). As a possible analog here, we consider this e-Gravity as a property of ether field over space. For different reference systems, field strength and speed vary, so does this term. The variation is not due to cancelation by inertial force. It is due to differences on the field properties measured from different reference systems.

In general, by transforming the momentum equation to (12.1), we can respectively split the momentum change rate on the left-hand side and force on the right-hand side into several items. As the e-Gravity term shows up on both sides, it cancels itself from the equation. The details of this term thus can be temporarily “ignored” by this cancelation. If we find the solutions to equation (12.2), we can then calculate the gravity term from field strength and velocity, and add it back to both sides of the equation to find the total force and total momentum change rate.

Another important property of gravity is being proportional to gravitational mass. To have a more complete analogy to gravity, it is necessary to have a counterpart of gravitational mass in ether field and link force term \vec{G} to it. This is yet to be explored, especially after particle solutions of the field equations are found.

§13 Electromagnetic Interaction in Ether Field

Rewrite (12.2) and put it together with the ether equation, we have

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \Omega + \nabla \cdot (\Omega \vec{u}) = 0 \\ \frac{\partial}{\partial t} (\Omega \vec{u}) - \vec{u} \times (\nabla \times (\Omega \vec{u})) = -\nabla c^2 \Omega \end{array} \right. \quad (13.1)$$

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \Omega + \nabla \cdot (\Omega \vec{u}) = 0 \\ \frac{\partial}{\partial t} (\Omega \vec{u}) - \vec{u} \times (\nabla \times (\Omega \vec{u})) = -\nabla c^2 \Omega \end{array} \right. \quad (13.2)$$

Substitute the variables by $\varphi = c^2 \Omega$, $\vec{A} = \Omega \vec{u}$, $\vec{B} = \nabla \times \vec{A}$ and $\vec{E} = \vec{B} \times \vec{u}$, the above equations become

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \frac{1}{c^2} \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \varphi + \nabla \cdot \bar{A} = 0 \\ \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \bar{A} + \bar{E} = -\nabla \varphi \end{array} \right. \quad (13.3)$$

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \frac{1}{c^2} \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \varphi + \nabla \cdot \bar{A} = 0 \\ \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \bar{A} + \bar{E} = -\nabla \varphi \end{array} \right. \quad (13.4)$$

In appearance, if we make analogies between \bar{E} , \bar{B} , φ , \bar{A} and the related properties in electromagnetic field (i.e., electric field, magnetic field, electric potential and magnetic vector potential, respectively), (13.3) is exactly the Lorentz gauge condition and (13.4) is one of the Maxwell equations.

Furthermore, from $\bar{B} = \nabla \times \bar{A}$, we have

$$\nabla \cdot \bar{B} = 0 . \quad (13.5)$$

Taking curl of (13.4), we have

$$\frac{\partial \bar{B}}{\partial t} = -\nabla \times \bar{E} . \quad (13.6)$$

Taking divergence of (13.4) and curl of $\bar{B} = \nabla \times \bar{A}$, applying Lorentz gauge condition, we can further obtain the wave equations for the two potentials:

$$\frac{1}{c^2} \frac{\partial^2 \varphi}{\partial t^2} - \nabla^2 \varphi = \nabla \cdot \bar{E} \quad (13.7)$$

$$\frac{1}{c^2} \frac{\partial^2 \bar{A}}{\partial t^2} - \nabla^2 \bar{A} = -\frac{1}{c^2} \frac{\partial \bar{E}}{\partial t} + \nabla \times \bar{B} \quad (13.8)$$

Except for that electric charge and current are not yet involved, all these equations ((13.3) ~ (13.8)) are exactly the same in appearance as the Maxwell equations (with Lorentz gauge condition).

These surprising similarities naturally lead to a conjecture that electromagnetic field may be explainable/interpretable by ether field, or may actually be just the above alternative forms of ether field.

Note that the electromagnetic field in our current understanding is based on electric charge (and current, moment) of particles, and particles are expected to be ether field structures. In this sense, electromagnetic field in our current understanding is at “particle level”, while the ether field properties used in the above analogy are at “ether field level”. Further details will need to be explored for the analogy here which is trying to link properties in different levels. Especially, we will need a counterpart for electric charge in the (yet to be obtained) particle solutions of the ether field equations to make the analogy complete.

Historically, there have been similar attempts to analogize electromagnetic field theory to fluid dynamics. It is Maxwell who in the years he was constructing the electromagnetic theory first suggested that vector potential behaves like a moving medium^[11]. Examples of more recent attempts can be found in publications like [12] and [13]. All these analogies seem revealing some similar similarity between

electromagnetic field and fluids. Most of the previous attempts are based on the fluid model described by Navier-Stokes equations. The suggested analogy in this paper however, is based on ether field. As a new medium model, ether has some unique features compared to Navier-Stokes fluids. This brings some detailed differences for the above analogy.

Obviously, the analogy here, if stands, may bring some totally new understanding for the electromagnetic field, as well as a series of new properties and consequences, which are yet to be further explored/examined.

For example, the scalar potential $\varphi = c^2\Omega$ and vector potential $\vec{A} = \Omega\vec{u}$ are now directly related to each other. The latter is just the flow of the former. Similar is for electric field $\vec{E} = \vec{B} \times \vec{u}$ and magnetic field \vec{B} . In this case, \vec{E} is relying on \vec{B} . Wherever \vec{E} exists, \vec{B} has to be non-zero. Also, \vec{E} and \vec{B} will be orthogonal to each other. All these need to be further examined in details, especially when particle solutions of the ether field are available and electric charge has a counterpart on the solutions.

Another feature brought by this analogy is that Lorentz gauge condition is now mandatory, as it is just an alternative form of ether conservation.

At the same time, momentum equation (12.2) can be rewritten in “force format” as

$$\frac{2\Omega}{c^2} \frac{\partial}{\partial t} (\Omega\vec{u}) - \frac{2\Omega}{c^2} \vec{u} \times (\nabla \times (\Omega\vec{u})) = -\nabla\Omega^2 = -\frac{2\Omega}{c^2} \nabla c^2\Omega.$$

Denote $\rho = \frac{2\Omega}{c^2}$ and do the substitution with the electromagnetic terms, the above equation becomes

$$\rho \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial t} \vec{A} + \vec{E} \right) = -\rho \nabla \varphi. \quad (13.9)$$

This is the force related to the analogized electromagnetic field, i.e., the “ether level” of Lorentz force. We will borrow one more name and call it “e-Lorentz force” hereafter.

Recall that the right-hand side of the momentum equation (12.1) contains two terms of force. The first term was considered as a gravity-like force while now the second term is considered as field level of Lorentz force. From ether field point of view, these are the only two kinds of force in the field. For complicated field structures, these two force terms can be complicated. But if described by field equations, all force can always be split to two portions, namely e-Gravity and e-Lorentz force, as the two terms on the right-hand side of (12.1).

In current electromagnetic field and gravity theories, electric charge is source of electric field. It is considered a property of particles and is carried by the particles, thus is concentrated at a point (for point-particles) or in a small volume (for non-point-particles). Similar is for gravitational mass. On the other hand, electric field and gravity field around are considered created by the charge and mass, proportional to amount of the charge/mass and anti-proportional to square of distance.

From ether field point of view, however, particles are conjectured as non-local field structures. A particle is not concentrated at a point or in a small volume. The field is the particle itself, rather than the “force field” it generates. Wherever the force exists, the field there is part of the particle structure.

In short-range, the particle solutions may have complicated structures and the two force terms (i.e., e-Gravity and e-Lorentz) can be complicated, especially when two or more particles are close to each other. In our current understanding, there are four kinds of force in particle level (i.e., EM interaction, strong interaction, weak interaction and gravity). These could be the equivalent effects of the two force terms and their combinations. In long-range, the overall effects of e-Gravity and e-Lorentz force on a whole particle might converge to the inverse-square gravity and Lorentz force of our normal understanding.

If this is the case, the particle properties like charge and gravitational mass would be total effect of the related field properties, and could be calculated in certain way from the field level properties.

Generally speaking, when we calculate total effects by integrating certain properties over a volume in space, in certain cases (e.g., in inverse square field), the integral could be a fix value if certain point or region is included, and vanishes otherwise. If this is the case for the particle solutions, it may explain the concentration of electric charge and gravitational mass in our current understanding. The concentration of charge and mass on point-particles could actually be a mathematical effect rather than a real physical distribution, from ether theory point of view.

On the other hand, as the field properties like strength, velocity and vorticity are being linked to electromagnetic properties by the analogy, so could the gravity-like force term. We can rewrite this term as $\vec{G} = \nabla \frac{\Omega^2 u^2}{c^2} = \nabla \frac{A^2}{c^2}$, and A here is just the vector potential according to the analogy. In other word, the e-Gravity could be calculated from vector potential (as an “electromagnetic property” in ether field), and is linked to the e-Lorentz force $-\rho \nabla \phi$. This is a significant consequence that (if analogized to the case of normal gravity and Lorentz force) does not seem seen in known observations of gravity and electromagnetic field (nor, though, does it seem clearly contradicting to known observations/experiments). This would be a strong requirement that needs to be met for the analogies to gravity and electromagnetic force to stand. We can use it as a hard standard in the future to examine any further detailed analogy brought by particle solutions and counterparts of electric charge and gravitational mass.

§14 Steady Solutions

Obviously, seeking for solutions of field equations to analogize particles is an essential goal for this proposed ether field theory. In certain degree, this is to reactivate Lord Kelvin’s “vortex atom” conjecture in a new way and to pursue the ambition Lord Kelvin and many others have had since then.

In this and the following sections, we will discuss about the overall view of the equations and the possible “particle solutions”, the relation/similarity to the fluid dynamics open problem, and a special

solution as example for further discussion. In an approximate way, we will also discuss about the possible interpretation of light and photons, as well as particles and anti-particles from ether field point of view.

As the exact general solutions are still yet to be obtained, most of the discussions in the rest of this paper are just as conjectures or preliminary thoughts, which hopefully might provide some clues for further exploration beyond this paper.

As discussed in §10, there must be a background field (BGF) that suffuses throughout the whole space to provide a positive pressure as boundary conditions. Field structures are then expected to exist inside the background field, as solutions of the field equations with the boundary conditions.

According to the equations and the properties discussed in previous sections, there can be all kinds of motions in the field. Among them can be some central motions that form vortex-like structures in the field. In those structures, pressure near the structure center should be in general lower than pressure in the surrounding field, so that the gradient of pressure can provide the necessary centripetal force to support the central motions. This kind of structures, if stable, would be the field structures we are looking for to analogize particles (namely the “particle solutions”).

In general, particles are moving relative to each other (and relative to BGF). So a particle (as a field structure) in general would not be steady. To simplify the discussion however, we will first concentrate on the case of a steady flow in a stationary, flat and infinitely large GBF. This will allow us to explore the possible single particle solutions without inference from other particles.

In steady case, momentum equation (12.2) and the ether equation can be rewritten with the notations of $\bar{A} = \Omega \bar{u}$ and $\psi = \frac{c^2 \Omega^2}{2}$ as

$$\begin{cases} \bar{A} \times (\nabla \times \bar{A}) = \nabla \psi & (14.1) \\ \nabla \cdot \bar{A} = 0 & (14.2) \end{cases}$$

This is exactly the same as the steady Euler equations for incompressible fluids^{[14],[15]}.

Note that in appearance ether is “compressible”, as field density is not a constant. However, the corresponding steady Euler equation is the one for incompressible fluids. The flow density vector, \bar{A} , which is corresponding to velocity in incompressible fluids, is divergenceless.

Per (14.1), \bar{A} is perpendicular to $\nabla \psi$, hence $\bar{A} \cdot \nabla \psi = 0$. This further leads to $\bar{u} \cdot \nabla \Omega = 0$. In other words, ether velocity \bar{u} is perpendicular to gradient of ether strength in steady flow. Applying this to (14.2), we can further obtain $\nabla \cdot \bar{u} = 0$. That is, the velocity field in steady ether flow is also divergenceless.

With (14.1) and (14.2), every solution of incompressible Euler equations can be converted to a steady solution in ether field. In this way, the particle solutions we are seeking for are linked to the possible solutions of steady Euler equations in fluid mechanics.

Despite of great interest and efforts, general solution of the steady Euler equations is still an open problem in mechanics^[14]. It is part of the more general open problem of solving the Navier-Stokes equations, which is one of the Millennium Prize Problems by Clay Mathematics Institute^[15]. The research on this problem is ongoing actively, which hopefully will soon lead to the general solutions that will also benefit the study of ether field.

There are, however, some special solutions presented so far. We can use them as examples to preliminarily discuss about the possible interpretation of particles.

Assuming vector field \vec{A} is divergenceless (thus satisfies (14.2)), and is everywhere collinear to its curl, the left-hand side of (14.1) will vanish. If the field strength is uniform, the right-hand side of (14.1) also vanishes and (14.1) is satisfied. \vec{A} and ψ in this case form a solution of the equation system.

This is the Beltrami flow in fluids mechanics. The left-hand side of (14.1) (which is the Lamb vector of \vec{A}) is zero everywhere. In this case, \vec{A} and its curl are linked by a scalar function of space, denoted as λ . That is

$$\vec{A} = \lambda \nabla \times \vec{A} .$$

As \vec{A} is divergenceless, we have

$$\nabla \cdot \vec{A} = \nabla \cdot (\lambda \nabla \times \vec{A}) = 0, \text{ or } \nabla \lambda \cdot (\nabla \times \vec{A}) = 0 .$$

Except for $\nabla \times \vec{A} = 0$ (which is a trivial case), there are two cases for λ and \vec{A} to meet this condition. Either λ is a constant thus $\nabla \lambda = 0$ (in this case, \vec{A} is called a linear Beltrami flow) or when λ is not a constant (i.e., \vec{A} is a non-linear Beltrami flow) but $\nabla \lambda$ is everywhere perpendicular to \vec{A} .

A good example for linear Beltrami flow is the engine vector of the curl operator in sphere coordination system^[16]:

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} A_r = K_n n(n+1) r^{-3/2} J_{n+1/2}(r) P_n(\cos \theta) \\ A_\theta = K_n r^{-1/2} [J_{n-1/2}(r) - n J_{n+1/2}(r)/r] P_n^1(\cos \theta) \\ A_\varphi = -K_n r^{-1/2} J_{n+1/2}(r) P_n^1(\cos \theta) \end{array} \right. \quad \begin{array}{l} (14.3a) \\ (14.3b) \\ (14.3c) \end{array}$$

Here K_n is a constant; n is an integer (as index of the solution series); $J_{n+1/2}(r)$ is the Bessel function of the first kind; $P_{n-1}(\cos \theta)$ is the Legendre function and $P_n^1(\cos \theta)$ is the associated Legendre function.

This solution can be derived in a straightforward way by assuming the field is axisymmetric and the curl of the vector potential \vec{A} equals to \vec{A} itself in spherical coordinate system (r, θ, φ) . That is

$$\bar{\omega} = \nabla \times \bar{A} = \frac{1}{r \sin \theta} \left[\frac{\partial}{\partial \theta} (\sin \theta A_\phi) \right] \bar{e}_r - \frac{1}{r} \left[\frac{\partial}{\partial r} (r A_\phi) \right] \bar{e}_\theta + \frac{1}{r} \left[\frac{\partial}{\partial r} (r A_\theta) - \frac{\partial A_r}{\partial \theta} \right] \bar{e}_\phi = \bar{A}.$$

Also assume that A_ϕ is a function of r and θ with separable variables. In that case we can let $A_\phi = \omega_\phi = f(r, \theta) = R(r) \cdot \Theta(\cos \theta)$ and obtain a Legendre equation and a spherical Bessel equation for which solutions are

$$\Theta(\cos \theta) = C_1 P_n^1(\cos \theta) \text{ and } R(r) = C_2 \sqrt{\frac{\pi}{2}} r^{-1/2} J_{n+1/2}(r).$$

These give $f(r, \theta)$ and the three velocity components as in (14.3).

When $n = 0$, it is a stationary field (i.e., a trivial solution).

When $n = 1$, if we set the constant $K_1 = \frac{3\sqrt{2\pi}}{4} c \Omega$ (so that the maximum speed in the field equals to sound speed; field strength Ω is a constant here as assumed), velocity is

$$\begin{cases} u_r = \frac{3c}{r^3} (\sin r - r \cos r) \cos \theta & (14.4a) \end{cases}$$

$$\begin{cases} u_\theta = -\frac{3c}{2r^3} (r^2 \sin r - \sin r + r \cos r) \sin \theta & (14.4b) \end{cases}$$

$$\begin{cases} u_\phi = \frac{3c}{2r^2} (\sin r - r \cos r) \sin \theta & (14.4c) \end{cases}$$

The three velocity components and pressure (along radius, in the $\theta = \pi/2$ plane) are shown in Fig. 14-1.

Fig. 14-1: Velocity and pressure of the first order spherical solution ($n=1, \theta = \pi/2$)

At the radii where $\sin r - r \cos r = 0$, velocity components $u_r = 0, u_\theta = 0$ (and u_ϕ reaches local extremum). The field is separated by these nodal spheres into spherical layers, with one vortex-ring-like structure existing in each layer. Flow and pressure distribution are shown below in Fig. 14-2.

Fig. 14-2: Velocity and pressure of the first order spherical solution ($n=1$)

For higher order, i.e., $n \geq 2$, the whole field is also split into homocentric spherical layers, with n vortex rings in each layer. The flow and pressure for cases of $n=2$ and $n=3$ are shown below in Fig. 14-3 and Fig. 14-4, respectively.

Fig. 14-3: Velocity and pressure of the 2nd order spherical solution

Fig. 14-4: Velocity and pressure of the 3rd order spherical solution

There are other Beltrami flows presented. Some of them are physically less meaningful as solutions of the steady ether equations (e.g., periodic in space; with non-zero velocity in infinity, etc.). Related to Beltrami flows, the Kamchatnov-Hopf soliton^[3] has brought a lot of attention due to its nice features. But it is a solution of the magnetohydrodynamic equations (rather than the Euler equation). The Hopf fibration, if treated as a velocity field, is a (non-linear) Beltrami flow. But as the velocity is not divergenceless, it is not a solution of the steady ether equations (which require divergenceless velocity).

In a more general case, if we require non-zero value on both sides of (14.1), the flow becomes the generalized Beltrami flow in fluid mechanics. In this case, the field strength is not uniform, but velocity is still divergenceless and is everywhere perpendicular to gradient of the field strength.

There are some exact solutions for this case^{[17], [18], etc.}. Among them are a family of solutions related to Hill's spherical vortex^[19]. For them, vorticity only exists inside a spherical or ellipsoidal region (the vortex core), and vanishes elsewhere. If these solutions are interpreted as particles, certain properties will only exist inside the core and vanish outside.

§15 Particles and Properties

To link field structures to real particles, the properties of particles, like mass (gravitational and inertial), electric charge, momentum, etc., need to be linked to and explained by properties of the field. However, this will strongly rely on the (yet to be obtained) exact solutions. Before enough exact solutions are available for quantitative study, we can only try to qualitatively preview the possible aspects of the solutions, as well as the relations to the corresponding field properties.

As mentioned previously, so far the properties like mass, energy, force density, etc. are defined based on field, i.e., are at "field level". If steady solutions exist and are interpreted as particles, the overall

properties of the particle (i.e., the “particle level properties”) would need to be re-defined as certain integral of the field level properties.

In particle level, most of the properties are determined according to interactions (either the particle to particle interactions, or the interactions between particles and the “force field” they are in). From ether field point of view, force only exists between adjacent ether, and the “force field” is part of the particle structures. Thus, a particle involved with long range interactions can not be a point or in a small region. Those particles as field structures should normally be infinitely large. When interact with other particles, the field (and thus the particle itself) will change. In other words, interactions will unavoidably impact the particles themselves.

As discussed, there are only two kinds of force at field level: e-Gravity and e-Lorentz force. These two forces are thus expected to be related to the particle level kinetic properties (mass, momentum, energy, etc.) and the electromagnetic properties (charge, magnetic moment, etc.). However, the particle properties might not be just simply the integral of the field level properties over space.

In principle, to understand the exact interaction between two particles, it would be necessary to find a solution of the field equations with two particle-like structures co-existing in the same boundary conditions. This could be complicated and would normally be a dynamic solution rather than a steady one. Exact interaction between multiple particles would be even more complicated, and likely will need to be studied with approximate and/or statistical methods.

As a preliminary attempt however, we can take the spherical vortex solution discussed in last section to exam some properties of the e-Gravity and e-Lorentz force terms.

For this solution, as field strength Ω is a constant, e-Lorentz force vanishes everywhere. If electric charge is relying on e-Lorentz force only and this solution is interpreted as a particle, it must be an electroneutral one. This applies to other solutions with linear Beltrami flow as well.

On the other hand, vector potential $\vec{A} = \Omega \vec{u}$ and its curl are non-zero almost everywhere (except for the sphere center), thus a non-zero magnetic field $\vec{B} = \nabla \times \vec{A}$ exists. But as \vec{B} and \vec{u} are everywhere parallel, electric field $\vec{E} = \vec{B} \times \vec{u}$ is always zero.

For a solution with generalized Beltrami flow (which has non-zero Lamb vector), electric field will not be everywhere zero. For instant, Hill’s spherical vortex, if considered as a particle, will have non-zero electric and magnetic fields inside the core sphere. However, the exact meaning of these related to the electrical charge and magnetic moment of the whole particle is not very clear yet.

With solution (14.4), we have

$$\begin{aligned} u^2 &= \frac{9c^2}{4r^6} (2r^2 \cos^2 r - 6r \sin r \cos r - 3\cos^2 r - r^4 + r^2 + 3) \cos^2 \theta \\ &\quad + \frac{9c^2}{4r^6} (2r^2 \cos^2 r - 2r \sin r \cos r - \cos^2 r + r^4 - r^2 + 3) \\ &= T_1(r) \cos^2 \theta + T_2(r) \end{aligned}$$

$(T_1(r), T_2(r))$ are denotations for convenience in following discussion.)

e-Gravity term thus is

$$\vec{G} = \nabla \frac{\Omega^2 u^2}{c^2} = \frac{\Omega^2}{c^2} \nabla u^2 = \frac{\Omega^2}{c^2} (T_1'(r) \cos^2 \theta + T_2'(r)) \vec{e}_r - \frac{\Omega^2}{c^2 r} T_1(r) \sin(2\theta) \vec{e}_\theta.$$

Obviously, with θ existing in the above equations, e-Gravity in this case is not only in the radial direction. It also exists in the latitude direction \vec{e}_θ and varies with θ . The force component in radial direction is dependent on θ as well.

When r is small (i.e., close to “particle center”), e-Gravity changes greatly with r . In the far field, except for certain polar angles (i.e., at both poles and the equator), components of the e-Gravity term in both radial and latitude directions are approaching r^{-3} .

Note that this is within a single field structure. It is the “gravity density” applies to the field in the solution. This in appearance is quite different than the gravity in normal understanding between particles, which is only in radial direction, exactly spherical symmetric and inverse-square. More details of these discrepancies will need to be further explored.

To interpret particles as ether field structures, there is another important feature yet to be explored. In real physical world, each particle (in static state) has special and fixed value of mass (energy), charge, etc. For an ether structure to be linked to these fixed properties, the structure needs to have fixed dimension and a fixed field strength distribution, as well as a fixed velocity field.

As the basic equations are homogeneous to field strength, the field strength in the particle can be proportional to the field strength in boundary condition (i.e., proportional to strength of BGF). A possible case is that particles under the same boundary conditions have fixed ratio on mass and certain other properties, but when boundary conditions (BGF) change, the absolute quantity of the properties will change proportionally.

Sound speed provides an upper limit for velocity field, but whether this limit is reached in each stable solution remains a question. Similar situation is for absolute dimensions of field structures.

Overall, there must be certain mechanism (e.g., maximized or minimized of certain action) to determine the stability of field structures and decide the fixed strength, fixed velocity and fix dimension of them, hence explain the fixed (and quantized) properties of particles. This is a missing part of the whole conjecture that is yet to be found.

§16 Particle, Antiparticle and Photon

According to (12.2) or (13.9), (14.1), in steady solutions, e-Lorentz force equals to the Lamb vector of vector potential, i.e. $\nabla \psi = \vec{A} \times (\nabla \times \vec{A})$. The angle between \vec{A} and its curl $\nabla \times \vec{A}$ thus plays an important role.

In the Beltrami flow case, \bar{A} and its curl are collinear and Lamb vector vanishes. In principle, this can happen with two non-trivial cases (i.e., $\nabla \times \bar{A} \neq 0$): curl is parallel or anti-parallel to the vector potential.

For example, in an axisymmetric case, if vector field $\bar{A} = (A_r, A_\theta, A_\phi)$ is divergenceless and \bar{A} is everywhere parallel to $\nabla \times \bar{A}$, vector field $\bar{A}^* = (A_r, A_\theta, -A_\phi)$ would also be divergenceless and is anti-parallel to its curl $\nabla \times \bar{A}^*$. Both \bar{A} and \bar{A}^* have vanished Lamb vector and satisfy the steady equations (14.1)/(14.2), thus both are solutions.

In this case, \bar{A} and \bar{A}^* are chiral symmetrical to each other. As \bar{A} and \bar{A}^* have the same magnitude for each vector component, if both are considered as particle solution, the two particles will have some similar or related properties. For example, as Lamb vector vanishes, e-Lorentz force is zero in either case. Thus the two particles would be both electroneutral. They can also have the same gravitational mass in particle level. However, the angular momentum along Z-axis would be opposite to each other due to different chirality.

In certain degree, this seems matching the case of an electroneutral particle-antiparticle pair (e.g., neutron and antineutron).

For the generalized Beltrami flow case, \bar{A} and its curl is not everywhere collinear. Lamb vector thus is not everywhere zero. In the axisymmetric case, if vector field $\bar{A} = (A_r, A_\theta, A_\phi)$ and its curl form a directional angle of θ , by changing direction, chirality or magnitude of components, etc., there might be three other cases related to \bar{A} and have the directional angle from vector potential to its curl as $-\theta$ and $\pi - \theta$, $\pi + \theta$, respectively. A possible conjecture is that these four cases (including \bar{A}) might form two charged particle/antiparticle pairs (like electron-antielectron, proton-antiproton).

On the other hand, mathematically, there are plenty of vortex-filament-like solutions for the steady equations. In cylindrical coordinate system, if the steady flow is axisymmetric and is uniform along z-axis, i.e., $u_r = 0$, $u_z = u_z(r)$, $u_\theta = u_\theta(r)$, $\Omega = \Omega(r)$, $\frac{\partial}{\partial t} = 0$, $\frac{\partial}{\partial \theta} = 0$, $\frac{\partial}{\partial z} = 0$, the momentum equation in r-direction becomes

$$\frac{\partial(c^2\Omega^2 - \Omega^2u_\theta^2 - \Omega^2u_z^2)}{\partial r} = \frac{2\Omega^2u_\theta^2}{r}. \quad (16.1)$$

If we further have $u_z = 0$ (i.e., a non-swirl flow), the equation is

$$\frac{\partial(c^2\Omega^2 - \Omega^2u_\theta^2)}{\partial r} = \frac{2\Omega^2u_\theta^2}{r}. \quad (16.2)$$

Let $p(r)$ be a differentiable function of r ($r \geq 0$), positive and monotonically increasing (i.e., $p > 0$ and $p' = \frac{dp(r)}{dr} > 0$), then $\Omega = \sqrt{p + \frac{rp'}{2}}$, $u_\theta = c\sqrt{\frac{rp'}{2p + rp'}}$ would be a solution of (16.2), and $p(r)$ in this case is pressure of the non-swirl flow.

For the swirl flow case ($u_z \neq 0$), we have the freedom to pick proper functions as pressure $p(r)$ and swirl speed u_z to construct solutions for equation (16.1). As a simple example, if we let $u_z = u_\theta = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}\tilde{u}$, (16.1) becomes

$$\frac{\partial(c^2\Omega^2 - \Omega^2\tilde{u}^2)}{\partial r} = \frac{\Omega^2\tilde{u}^2}{r},$$

and $\Omega = \sqrt{p + rp'}$, $\tilde{u} = c\sqrt{\frac{rp'}{p + rp'}}$ is a solution (with same assumption on $p(r)$ as above).

The vortex filaments in these solutions (swirl or non-swirl) are straight and infinitely long. They may or may not exist in the field with the exact aspects as in these solutions. However, for a vortex-sphere-like or vortex-ring-like particle solution, in the far-field range along the symmetry axis, the flow can be approximated as a vortex filament (Fig. 16-1). By considering the properties of vortex filaments, we might be able approximate the possible behavior in the far field of the particle solutions along the symmetry axis.

Fig. 16-1: Far-field, near-axis flow of a swirl vortex ring may be approximated as a vortex filament

In fluid mechanics, vortex filaments are being carefully studied. For the vortex filaments that are solutions of incompressible Euler equations, Hasimoto applied the Local Induction Approximation (LIA) and describe motion of filaments by the nonlinear Schrödinger equation (NLSE) ^[20]. Soliton solutions can then be obtained for the NLSE.

If similar approximation can be applied to the filament-like flow in the far-field/near-axis regions of particle solutions, and also leads to NLSE, the soliton waves along the filament would be a good analogy for photons. (Also see similar analogy/analysis made by V.P. Dmitriyev^[8]).

Qualitatively speaking, when a particle is “accelerated” (i.e., the near-center portion of the particle solution entirely change motion status), a perturbation wave would be generated along the filament. This is similar to the case of a photon emitting from an accelerated charged particle.

Furthermore, if photons are soliton wave packets in the filaments, a natural explanation could be offered on why light is transverse and with linear/circular polarization. Many packets moving together could form the electromagnetic wave (light) of our normal understanding. But in fine details these wave packets are separated. This might bring an explanation for the concept of photon.

The NLSE solitons are moving along the filament and each soliton is in a fixed speed (related to the shape of the soliton, so it is not a common speed for all solitons). In a particle solution, the symmetric axis is a straight line (unless the particle is strongly impacted by other particles and loses symmetry). This might explain why photons propagate along straight lines. (However, as the speed varies for different solitons, it is not directly matching the fixed/common speed of light. The relation of the soliton speed to the sound speed in the field is also unclear yet.)

As shape and speed are unchanged, the extra energy a soliton wave packet brings to the filament would be fixed and related to features of the packet (e.g., the wavelength). This may explain the quantum feature of light, and might even lead to a quantitative explanation and exact calculation for the Planck constant.

With different values of the parameters, the soliton wave could be in different shapes. In certain cases, the filament might break and re-connect itself and form new vortex rings, as new particles. This might imply an explanation of the electron-pair-effect.

Again, these are just rough conjectures so far. Further explorations are needed and will be relying on the yet to be obtained exact solutions of the fundamental equation system.

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